

D2.2

Final Report on Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation

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1. Executive Summary

This communication and dissemination final report assesses how and where the results of CLS INFRA were disseminated and valorised across all appropriate user communities. CLS INFRA has succeeded in creating and training a global network of scholars and practitioners of CLS methods and the WP2 Communication team has been instrumental in broadening the community and deepening its engagement.

The report will demonstrate our efforts to reach the communities we set out to target, and will show how the following aims and objectives, outlined in [“CLS INFRA D2.1 Communication and Dissemination Plan”](#), were addressed and fulfilled:

- Disseminate the project goals and outcomes effectively;
- Roll out efficient tools for communication with different stakeholders (online and offline);
- Build a vibrant community of stakeholders that will assist in expanding the project’s reach to underrepresented constituencies;
- Exploit the synergies in liaisons and collaborations with other infrastructures and groups;
- Recruit new users across all levels of expertise;
- Publicise and promote CLS INFRA events.

The report will link targets identified in [“CLS INFRA D2.1 Communication and Dissemination Plan”](#) to quantifiable outcomes and will further analyse meaningful responses from our target communities with a view to assessing the overall impact and effectiveness of communication strategies on the project. The report will include recommendations for future undertakings based on the experiences and observations of project members, as well as collected data.

The original Communication Plan, based on the project aims and objectives articulated in the Grant Proposal, underwent a major scheduled revision midway through the project in 2024 (Version 2.1) as we took stock of project progress and worked to continually adapt our strategies in response to the evolving digital humanities landscape and in light of the challenges posed by a global pandemic.

Overall, this report demonstrates the success of the CLS INFRA project communications in achieving objectives, responding to challenging and changing pressures in the field, and completing tasks above and beyond those planned to reach our goals.

2. Introduction and Evolution of Work

2.1. Project Summary

The CLS INFRA (Computational Literary Studies Infrastructure) project aimed to transform how European literary heritage was accessed, studied, and shared by consolidating fragmented resources and building a sustainable research infrastructure for computational literary studies (CLS). Recognising that literature serves as a rich archive of human values, norms, and creativity, the project was founded on the premise that literary texts are not only cultural artefacts but also valuable sources of data. It responded to a growing community of researchers using computational methods to investigate Europe’s multilingual and interconnected literary history.

Despite longstanding efforts across Europe to digitise literary texts and make them accessible, the digital landscape remained highly uneven. Some regions and languages enjoyed robust digital coverage, while others were underrepresented. Moreover, existing corpora and tools were often isolated or incompatible, impeding cross-border and cross-linguistic research. CLS INFRA addressed this challenge by integrating and expanding efforts from earlier initiatives such as COST Action 16204 “Distant Reading,” the POSTDATA project, and the DraCor corpus, unifying them within a coherent infrastructure designed to serve both researchers and institutions.

At its core, the project sought to provide unified, easy access to high-quality literary data and analytical tools. It focused particularly on narrative prose, poetry, and drama, aiming to make data FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable) and compliant with legal and technical standards. The participation of key infrastructures like DARIAH ERIC and CLARIN ensured that the project’s results were not only widely adopted but also sustainable within broader European digital research environments.

CLS INFRA placed a strong emphasis on community engagement. It mapped user requirements within the CLS community and designed API-enabled “Programmable Corpora” to bridge the gap between user needs and the fragmented reality of existing resources. The project developed and optimised Natural Language Processing tools, workflows, and training materials to support both new and experienced users in applying computational methods to literary research.

Inclusivity was a key driver of CLS INFRA's work. The project actively supported participation by researchers from underrepresented regions and backgrounds, creating accessible training and outreach opportunities through initiatives like Transnational Access Fellowships and online courses. It also considered the needs of non-academic users such as educators, heritage professionals, and citizen scientists, ensuring that the tools and data were relevant and usable across a range of audiences.

Through a series of collaborative initiatives, including training schools, policy engagement, and shared resource development, CLS INFRA fostered networks of scholarly exchange and institutional cooperation. Its outputs included integrated tools, multilingual corpora, documentation toolkits, policy briefs, and explainer videos, all designed to advance the digital transformation of literary studies.

Ultimately, CLS INFRA created the foundations for a cohesive, inclusive, and technologically advanced research ecosystem in the field of CLS. By addressing infrastructural fragmentation and promoting methodological innovation, the project made a lasting contribution to understanding and preserving Europe's complex literary heritage.

2.2. Summaries of additional communications and dissemination tasks

During the CLS INFRA project lifetime WP2 responded to various opportunities and threats by returning to the main objectives outlined in "[CLSIINFRA D2.1 Communication and Dissemination Plan](#)" and responding appropriately. This meant, e.g., analysing the changing patterns of social media use by our main audiences and determining which channels would best reach them, or addressing the challenges in communications due to the COVID pandemic by investigating the processes of communication happening within the CLS INFRA project. Additionally, in 2024, CLS INFRA applied for and received a six-month extension to undertake further training and additional dissemination and valorisation. Thus communications work was required beyond the plans outlined in "[CLSIINFRA D2.1 Communication and Dissemination Plan](#)". This section identifies these tasks, undertaken over and above the initial project proposal. The additional tasks they identify will be expanded upon throughout the report.

2.2.1. Challenges of the COVID pandemic

The project's beginning in 2021 was overshadowed by the COVID pandemic. Though personal contact is important to develop communities of users, teachers and researchers, it was vital to adhere to all local guidelines for travel and contact. Thus gatherings including meetings of consortium partners, public-facing dissemination events, Transnational Access (TNA) Fellowships and training events were quickly adjusted. Asynchronous training materials and virtual meeting platforms were implemented with recordings made and disseminated where appropriate. Scheduling of TNA fellowships was also adjusted. Responsive communication of these adaptations across all channels was key to the project's success.

2.2.2. Revision of "[CLSIINFRA D2.1 Communication and Dissemination Plan](#)"

In 2023, several revisions were made to the reporting and measurement framework of "[CLSIINFRA D2.1 Communication and Dissemination Plan](#)" to more accurately reflect the progress and timeline of CLS INFRA activities. The measurement period for tool usage was extended to the post-M48 phase, just before final reporting, to account for the fact that most tools would not be available until the later stages of the project. Accordingly, usage targets were adjusted downward. The types of targets associated with the use of transformation tools were clarified, and the measurement period for these was similarly extended to ensure accurate capture of late-stage engagement.

Targets related to support services, particularly those concerning community-building, were revised to better reflect the active role of CLS INFRA team members as facilitators and instructors during events. Usage targets for online training materials were also adjusted to more realistic levels, based on observed engagement trends. A review of similar projects and current CLS INFRA engagement informed updates to various table targets; this included a reduction in the expected number of TNA Fellows per year (from 8–10 to 7–9), and an increase in projected institutional partners (from 14 to 15), based on data from rounds 1–5 of the TNA application process and evolving partnerships in 2023.

Additionally, new opportunities and threats were identified and integrated into the relevant tables, with COVID-related threats removed as their significance diminished. Dissemination strategies were refined to more closely align with specific audience groups, with infographics highlighted as a key communication method and progress noted on other outputs such as

policy briefs. Table 8 was updated to include Mastodon as a social media channel, to expand Twitter/X link coverage, and to confirm the use of email in conjunction with Mattermost. It also indicated a strategic expansion from Twitter/X into Mastodon, consistent branding across YouTube video content, and new detail regarding the TNA archive and videos, including a target number of videos. Updates also revised the primary news dissemination channels and recognised the value of interactive and accessible deliverables on the CLS INFRA website, such as the tool for exploring D3.2 (Survey of Methods) and the publication and presentation library.

2.2.3. Changing social media landscape

As Twitter/X lost popularity and fragmented into many social media communities in 2023, increases in the number of CLS INFRA followers slowed significantly. Responding to this, CLS INFRA started a Mastodon account in March 2023 and a BlueSky account in November 2024. In conjunction with outreach materials that target non-academic users, a social media push in 2024 significantly expanded into the social media spheres of cultural / historical institutions and citizen science, followed by additional social media pushes in 2025 targeting policy makers and GLAM institutions.

Additionally, after the second Training School event in Madrid, participants suggested that there be an associated Discord server to continue the conversation. CLS INFRA project team member Artjoms Šeļa started and curated the [Latent Reading Discord Community](#), with more than 150 members as of summer 2025, to meet this need.

2.2.4. Infographics

As part of the 2024 social media push, CLS INFRA sought to expand into the spheres of cultural / historical institutions and citizen science using a set of four Infographics based on the work of “[CLSIINFRA D3.5 User Needs Beyond Academic Research for Computational Literary Analysis](#)”. These were undertaken to provide direct, accessible messaging on CLS tools and methods to several target groups outlined in that plan, modified after the analysis completed in CLS INFRA D3.5.

2.2.5. Internal Communications Survey

Work Package 2 developed an internal communications survey, as the disruption of the pandemic makes such review of primary importance. In the survey we evaluated the forms

of communication most used and most useful, and the perspective of team members on how strong internal communications are and how well they have functioned.

2.2.6. Further training in 2025

This training was targeted to the specific needs of the user base for CLS tools and methods. Constructing a survey from the categories listed in “[CLS INFRA D4.1 Skills Gap Analysis](#)”, we emailed 305 potential participants including all applicants, successful and unsuccessful, to the TNA Fellowship Programme, and all participants in the three training schools. By analysing the results of the survey, examples of which are included as 8.3: Appendix 3: Results of Further Training Survey, we then determined that workshops on Network Analysis and Textometry best matched the continuing needs of our user base. The first, in online hands-on format, was dedicated to Network Analysis and taught by Daniil Skorinkin from the University of Potsdam on 9 July 2025. The workshop had over 80 participants and received high praise. The second workshop, on Textometry, is taught by Serge Heiden from University of Lyon and presented in asynchronous video format; it is in the final stages of production and will be released and advertised in the autumn. Both recordings will be hosted on the CLS INFRA YouTube channel ([@clsinfra6863](#)) and DARIAH Campus along with other training resources of the project, and valorised on our website ([CLSINFRA.io](#)) and social media channels Twitter/X ([@CLSinfra](#)), Mastodon([@CLSinfra@fedihum.io](#)), BlueSky ([@CLSinfra.bsky.social](#)), and in the project newsletter.

3. Targets and Results

3.1. Overall objectives

The overall aim of the CLS INFRA project was to create unified and easy access to the best European and national infrastructures for the CLS community which has not been fully supported to benefit from the existing infrastructures and data resources. The project therefore consolidated, integrated and further developed institutional, national and regional efforts to build shared and sustainable access to the high-quality data, tools, and knowledge in the field of literary studies, in general, and CLS, in particular.

To achieve this overall aim, CLS INFRA has pursued the following specific objectives. This section of this report provides lists of key outputs and quantitative analysis. See Section 4 for audience-centred impact analysis and Section 5 for content analysis.

3.1.1. Objective 1:

Bridging knowledge-based resources for CLS community: Over the lifetime of the project, CLS INFRA has built on existing European and national infrastructures to significantly reconfigure access paradigms for literary data (including narrative prose, poetry and drama), vastly improving its adherence to the FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable, reusable) principles, and enhancing tools for extracting, disseminating, and documenting literary works within the constraints of existing copyright laws.

OBJECTIVE 1		
Bridging knowledge-based resources for CLS community		
Target Outcome	Indicator	Target
Publication of reports on existing resources in CLS	Completed reviews of ecosystems for literary data (D5.1), inventory of existing data sources and formats (D6.1), programmable corpora (D7.1), APIs and corpora (D7.3, 7.4), NLP tools and processes (D8.1, 8.2)	O1.a: 7 reports: Achieved, see below. ¹
Scientific output on knowledge-based resources for CLS	Number of scientific journal articles	O1.b: 3 articles: Achieved, see below.
	Number of scientific conference papers / posters	O1.c: 3 papers/posters: Achieved, see below.

Table 1: Objective 1

O1.a List of reports on existing resources in CLS INFRA:

- Birkholz, Julie M., Silvie Cinková, Matthieu Decorde, Serge Heiden, Maarten Janssen, Michal Křen, Alvaro Perez Pozo, Victor Diego Fresno Fernandez, and Salvador Ros. "CLS INFRA D8.2 Report and Prototypes for Annotation as Enrichment," February 28, 2024. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11093999>.

¹ In CLS INFRA D2.1: Communications Plan v1, this measure was 7 Reports. In v2 (2023) it was altered to 10 Reports to account for three reports on Training Schools not considered in the initial plan. However, these reports are more properly included in measures addressing Objective 5. Thus in this report the original measure of 7 reports is restored.

- Börner, Ingo, and Peer Trilcke. “CLS INFRA D7.1 On Programmable Corpora,” February 28, 2023. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7664964>.
- Börner, Ingo, Peer Trilcke, Daniil Skorinkin, and Luca Giovannini. “CLS INFRA D7.4 Report on the Implementation of Programmable Corpora.” April 30, 2025. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15301341>.
- Cinková, Silvie, Julie M. Birkholz, Ingo Börner, Tess Dejaeghere, Serge Heiden, Maarten Janssen, Michal Křen, Salvador Ros, and Alvaro Perez Pozo. “CLS INFRA D8.1 Report of the Tools for the Basic Natural Language Processing (NLP) Tasks in the CLS Context,” March 9, 2023. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7951059>.
- Ďurčo, Matej, Vera Maria Charvat, Ingo Börner, Michał Mrugalski, and Carolin Odebrecht. “CLS INFRA D6.1 Inventory of Existing Data Sources and Formats,” July 27, 2022. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7520286>.
- Mrugalski, Michał, Carolin Odebrecht, Vera Charvat, Ingo Börner, and Matej Durco. “CLS INFRA D5.1. Review of the Data Landscape,” July 19, 2022. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6861022>.
- Trilcke, Peer, and Ingo Börner. “CLS INFRA D7.3 On Versioning Living and Programmable Corpora (Executable) Report and Prototypes for Reproducible Research,” February 27, 2024. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11081934>.

O1.b: List of scientific journal articles, with DOI: See 8.1: Appendix 1, List of Scientific Journal Articles.

O1.c: List of papers / posters: See 8.2: Appendix 2, Scientific Conference Papers / Posters.

3.1.2. Objective 2

Mapping and matching specific requirements of CLS community: CLS INFRA reports and other outputs have served to map user requirements specific to the CLS community and implement a tactical infrastructure as an ecosystem of API-enabled “Programmable Corpora” to bridge the gap between their requirements for effective, easy access and the realities of fragmented, protected, distinctive resources.

OBJECTIVE 2		
Mapping and matching specific requirements of CLS community		
Target Outcome	Indicator	Target

Publication of reports on present and future of CLS	Completed reviews of baseline methodological needs of CLS users (D3.1), skills matrix and gap analysis (D4.1), and roadmap for the future of CLS (D1.2).	O2.a: 3 reports. Achieved, see below.
Scientific output on key methodological concerns of CLS	Number of survey papers on key methodological concerns (D3.2).	O2.b: 5 papers. Achieved, see below.

Table 2: Objective 2

O2.a: Reports on present and future of CLS:

- Schöch, Christof, Evgeniia Fileva, and Julia Dudar. “CLS INFRA D3.1 Baseline Methodological User Needs Analysis”, 2022. [10.5281/zenodo.6389333](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6389333). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6389333>.
- Van Rossum, Lisanne M., and Artjoms Šeĵa. “CLS INFRA D4.1 Skills Gap Analysis,” February 28, 2022. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6401857>.
- Yakupova, Vera, and Jennifer Edmond. “CLS INFRA D1.2 Strategic Roadmap for Computational Literary Studies,” February 28, 2025. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15411438>.

O2.b: Survey papers on key methodological concerns:

- Schöch, Christof, Dudar, Julia, and Fileva, Evgeniia. “CLS INFRA D3.2 Series of Five Short Survey Papers on Methodological Issues.” Zenodo, March 31, 2023. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7782363>.

3.1.3. Objective 3

Developed new digital tools and services for CLS users: Integrated and optimised existing tools and services for the CLS community, including in the domain of Natural Language Processing (NLP), in order to build, share and sustain robust, reusable and standards-compliant workflows for CLS.

OBJECTIVE 3 Developing new digital tools and services for CLS users		
Target Outcomes	Indicator	Target
Use of transformation tools	Endorsement expressed by assigning stars and/or forking the code of the transformation	O3.a: >= 20. Achieved. See below.

	<p>toolbox on GitHub (D6.2)</p> <p>Endorsement expressed by by downloads of (D6.3) report.</p>	O3.b: ≥ 45 . Achieved. See below.
Use of API libraries	<p>Numbers of stars and forks on GitHub. Number of users on API logs. Usage statistics of the python library was tracked on https://libraries.io/pypi/pydracor; R on CRAN or similar service (D7.2)</p>	O3.c: ≥ 20 . Achieved, see below.
Use of NLP resources	<p>Stars and forks for Named Entities-extraction pipeline (D8.3), entity-relation-extraction prototype (D8.4), or sentiment analysis pipeline (D8.5)</p>	<p>O3.d: ≤ 10 users (not satisfactory) ≥ 10 users (satisfactory) Achieved, see below.</p>
Resources for data sharing	<p>Completion of toolkit report for data sharing between researchers and institutions (D5.3).</p>	O3.e: 1 Report. Achieved, see below.
Scientific output on development of digital tools and services for CLS	<p>Number of scientific journal articles</p> <p>Number of scientific conference papers / posters</p>	<p>O3.f: 3 articles. Achieved, see below.</p> <p>O3.g: 3 papers/posters. Achieved, see below.</p>

Table 3: Objective 3

O3.a: Use of transformation tools, stars or forks for “[CLSI INFRA D6.2 Transformation Toolbox & Ingest and Processing Workflow](#)”:

- ACDH-OEAW & VELD GitHub, 1 fork, 61 followers
- OEAW ClsCor resource, (not monitored for traffic).

O3.b: Use of transformation tools, downloads of “[CLSI INFRA D6.3 Standards Beyond TEI / Extended Transformation Matrix / Alternative Formats](#)”:

- as of 28 Aug 2025, 175 downloads.

O3.c: Use of API libraries, “[CLSI INFRA D7.2 API Libraries for R and Python for the Programmable Corpora Prototype “DraCor”](#)”: “[rdracor](#)” and “[pydracor](#)”

- as of 28 Aug 2025, 355 stars & forks over all repositories (DraCor) + 13 users of PyDracor on Libraries.io.

O3.d: Use of NLP resources

- As of 28 Aug 2025, 13 users at GitHub.

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- Birkholz, Julie, Silvie Cinková, Tess Dejaeghere, Michal Křen, Els Lefever, Maarten Janssen, Pranaydeep Singh, Salvador Ros, and Toma Tasovac. “CLS INFRA D8.3 Report on Applied NLP Named Entity Recognition.” Zenodo, February 28, 2025. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15037919>.
- Birkholz, Julie, Tess Dejaeghere, Els Lefever, Pranaydeep Singh, and Salvador Ros. “CLS INFRA D8.4 Report on NLP Relational Extraction (REX).” Zenodo, February 28, 2025. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15037844>.
- Birkholz, Julie, Tess Dejaeghere, Salvador Ros, Álvaro Pozo Pérez, and Pranaydeep Singh. “CLS INFRA D8.5 Report on Applied NLP Sentiment Analysis.” Zenodo, February 28, 2025. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15037959>.

O3.e: Resources for data sharing:

- Report: Gouzi, Françoise, Michal Mrugalski, and Carolin Odebrecht. “CLS INFRA D5.3 Toolkit Report for Data Sharing Between Researchers and Institutions in the Field of Literary Studies.” Zenodo, April 23, 2024. <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.12742612>. 20 downloads as of 28 Aug 2025.
- Website Resource: https://clsinfra.io/toolkit_data_sharing/. 263 Page Views as of 28 Aug 2025.
- Wiki: <https://data.clsinfra.io/> (Not monitored for traffic)

O3.f: Scientific output, journal articles. See 8.1 Appendix 1: List of Scientific Journal Articles.

O3.g: Scientific conference papers / posters. See 8.2 Appendix 2: Scientific Conference Papers / Posters.

3.1.4. Objective 4

Mainstreaming of new digital tools/services: CLS INFRA deepened, widened and consolidated the user base for CLS sources and methods by providing support services and training for using established and emerging cutting-edge methodologies; building user-friendly components to facilitate participation of users from underrepresented regions and languages; and analysing non-academic user needs for future development.

Training materials for CLS sources and methods come in three varieties: the materials and presentations from the three CLS INFRA training schools and additional training services added to the project plans in 2025, presentations by CLS INFRA staff and TNA fellows, and the publication of articles, datasets and notebooks relating to CLS INFRA deliverables and TNA projects.

Deliverable	Target Outcome	Target
Use of online training materials	Number of users by M24 Number of users by M48	O4.a: <= 500 (not satisfactory) >= 500 (satisfactory) <= 2000 (not satisfactory) >= 2000 (satisfactory) Achieved, see below:
Attendance at training events	Number of registrations per event	O4.b: <= 40 (not satisfactory) >= 40 (satisfactory) Achieved, see below.
New goal as of M48: Additional training in 2025	Workshops targeted toward needs expressed by TNA and Training School applicants.	O4.c: 15% response to survey on training needs. 3 workshops. Achieved, see below.
Attendance at community-building and satellite events. In particular we are interested in connecting with the ADHO Special Interest Groups: https://adho.org/special-interest-groups-sigs	Attendance at community-building and satellite events. ²	O4.d: <= 100 (not satisfactory) >= 100 (satisfactory) Achieved, see below.
Publications on CLS research	Completion of showcases of CLS research accompanied by explanatory papers (D3.3) and case studies in data preparation and sharing (D5.2)	O4.e: 4 showcases & papers: Achieved, see below. 3 case studies: Achieved, see below.
Publications on emerging trends in CLS	Number of position papers and pilot studies on emerging trends in CLS (D3.4)	O4.f 3 position papers 2 pilot studies Achieved, see below.

Table 4: Objective 4

² An error in CLS INFRA D2.1 Communications Plan listed the Target Outcome for this category as “Number of CLS INFRA Team members presenting or facilitating at these events”.

O4.a: Use of online training materials, Number of users by M24 and M48

- M24: 875 views of YouTube training videos.
- M48: 4632 views of online videos (as of 28 Aug 2025).
- Total videos on YouTube channel: 78
- 1539 page views of Survey of Methods tool
- 263 page views of Toolkit for Data Sharing

O4.b: Attendance at training events

- TS Prague, 2022: 200 applications, 40 participants (25 in person, 15 online)
- TS Madrid, 2023: 166 applications, 164 participants (34 in person, 130 online)
- TS Vienna 2024: 109 applications, 39 participants (in person only)

O4.c: Additional training in 2025

- This additional objective was added with the project extension M48-M54
- 15% response to survey. Survey sent to all applicants to TNA programme and all participants in training schools.

O4.d: Attendance at community-building and satellite events.

- Distant Reading closing event: 80
- Semantic Network Analysis workshop with Ghent CDH: 25
- Full Stack Feminism TNA session: 10
- Demo of NER tools: 15
- LREC-COLING2024 Pre-conference workshop: 15
- Data-driven Approaches to Ancient Languages (DAAL) Workshop: 30
- MAPS - the UGent periodical studies research group study day on digitization: 20
- DH2024 workshop with ADHO SIG-DLS: 50
- DARIAH-IE Seminar and Re-Launch, May 2025: 52
- DH2025 workshop with ADHO SIG-DLS: 90
- CLS INFRA mini-conference, CCLS2025: 46
- TOTAL: **433**

O4.e: Publications on CLS research.

- Andorfer, Peter, Ingo Börner, Vera Maria Charvat, Aitor Díaz, Julia Dudar, Matej Ďurčo, Evgeniia Fileva, et al. "CLS INFRA D3.3 Showcases for the Application of

CLS Methods and Tools.” April 3, 2024.

<https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10912516>.

- Mrugalski, Michał, Annika Blietz, Ingo Börner, Elisabeth Bauer, Vera Charvat, Matej Ďurčo, Sabine Laszakovits, and Stefan Resch. “CLS INFRA D5.2 Case Studies in Data Preparation and Sharing.” Zenodo, July 5, 2023. <https://zenodo.org/record/8115922>.

O4.f: Publications on emerging trends in CLS.

- Mrugalski, Havrylash, Julia, Evgeniia Fileva, Ruth Bruchertseifer, and Christof Schöch. “CLS INFRA D3.4 Position Papers and Pilot Studies on Emerging Trends in CLS,” March 31, 2025. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15131773>.

3.1.4.1. Additional details, Objective 4

Training Schools: The success of the communications strategy for CLS INFRA training schools can be measured in terms of applicants for each school, as noted in Table 4: Objective 4. Additionally, a review of engagement with the Twitter/X hashtag #CIsInfraTraining demonstrates a consistently growing number of impressions from around 600 to 1100 (example below). The use of video interviews with participants helps to continue this engagement after the close of a training school and direct interest to the training materials when they are published on DARIAH CAMPUS. Applicants and participants have anecdotally noted the usefulness of the CLS INFRA website pages on the training school, as they feature summaries, FAQs, schedules, links to materials needed, bios of instructors, information about the location including transit and tourism, interviews with participants, and details on past training schools. E.g., as noted in “[CLS INFRA D4.2 Final Report on Training Materials and Events](#)”, participants at the final event in Vienna were satisfied with the practical information and assistance provided beforehand (5.8 of 7), as well as on-site (6.2 of 7).

Figure 1: Post on Twitter/X demonstrating engagement with video of Training School participant taken in Madrid.

Attendance at community-building and satellite events: CLS INFRA effectively leveraged its international reputation to build communication pathways within the existing and potential CLS community. Attendance figures are given above. Some examples include: In 2022, CLS INFRA closely coordinated with the COST Action Distant Reading for European Literary History to host a final event and closing ceremony. Also in 2022, Ghent CDH hosted a Semantic Network Analysis workshop with Julie Birkholz facilitating. Sarah Hoover hosted a question and answer session on the TNA Fellowship programme at the Full Stack Feminism conference (Brighton, UK, Sept 2023). Tess Dejaghere, Julie Birkholz and Els Lefevre hosted an invited, hybrid event to discuss NER tools and give demonstrations to the extended Ghent CDH community in May 2024. CLS INFRA institutional partners ACDH-CH, DH-Potsdam, Ghent CDH, LINHD-UNED, the University of Galway, Charles University (CUNI), and Trier CDH hosted Research Lunches, Study Mornings, Mini-Conferences, workshops and seminars featuring TNA Fellows and their work.

In August 2024, the CLS INFRA team co-organised a day-long workshop at the ADHO conference DH2024 at George Mason University, Arlington VA, USA with the Special Interest Group Digital Literary Studies (SIG-DLS). This all-day workshop, titled

“Computational Literary Studies: How To Do Research Responsibly”, attracted an attendance of 50 and featured CLS INFRA project team members Maciej Eder, Joanna Byszuk and Artjoms Šeļa as well as presentations and lightning talks from an additional 30 participants.

The partnership between CLS INFRA and ADHO SIG-DLS continued in 2025 with a co-convened half-day workshop where Artjoms Šeļa, Evgeniia Fileva, Julia Dudar and Christof Schöch presented work along with 75 other participants, including 3 TNA fellows: Richard Změlík, Jana-Katharina Mende and Svetlana Yatsyk (for program see: <https://dls.hypotheses.org/1952>). Finally, a CLS INFRA workshop day preceded CCLS2025, where leaders of particular Work Packages presented CLS INFRA outputs and successes to 45 participants, and 7 invited TNA fellows gave talks on the research they conducted thanks to the project (see: <https://clsinfra.io/closing-event/>).

Completion of showcases of CLS research accompanied by explanatory papers (D3.3) and case studies in data preparation and sharing (D5.2):

- Andorfer, Peter, Ingo Börner, Vera Maria Charvat, Aitor Díaz, Julia Dudar, Matej Ďurčo, Evgeniia Fileva, et al. “CLS INFRA D3.3 Showcases for the Application of CLS Methods and Tools.” Edited by Christof Schöch, Evgeniia Fileva, and Julia Dudar, April 3, 2024. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10912516>.
- This research was valorised on the project outputs page of CLS INFRA, (<https://clsinfra.io/resources/outputs>), with announcements in the CLS INFRA newsletter, on social media, and in a poster presented at several conferences (UK/IE DH 2024, DH2024, DARIAH Annual Event 2024).

Please Pick up Your Spanners: Showcases for the Application of CLS Methods and Tools

The four showcases brought together in Deliverable 3.3 illustrate, in a concrete, visual and interactive way, how some of the key methods in CLS work when they are applied to collections of literary texts.

Multilingual Stylometry Showcase

- Designed for: scholars and students, linguists
- Topics: the intersection of language, corpus composition, and stylometric methods of authorship attribution.

Averell

- Designed for: scholars and students of poetry
- Function: to help scholars create their own corpora of poetry by merging different corpora together

Detecting Small Worlds in a Corpus of Thousands of Theater Plays

- Designed for: scholars and students with basic knowledge of network theory
- Topics: typology of theatre plays from a network perspective

Poetrylab + rantanplan

- Designed for: readers, scholars, researchers in linguistics, literature, and culture
- Topics: Spanish poetic forms

Figure 2: section of CLS INFRA poster 2024.

3.1.5. Objective 5

Strengthening a culture of cooperation: CLS INFRA has established sustainable networks of shared infrastructural practices to institutionalise and sustain training and scholarly exchange in order to enable systematic and meaningful cooperation between disciplines, communities, countries and languages. The Training Schools in Prague (2022), Madrid (2023), and Vienna (2024) resulted in evaluative reports that provide useful information on reaching and connecting our audiences to form effective cooperative networks. Thus in v2 of “[CLS INFRA D2.1 Communication and Dissemination Plan](#)”, we added a target of three such reports.

A website (<https://clsinfra.io>), was created and is hosted by IJP-PAN and maintained by University of Galway, on behalf of the Consortium. The CLS INFRA website was the central pillar of the CLS INFRA communication and dissemination strategy.

This website served as the main hub for all CLS INFRA stakeholder communities and anyone else interested in CLS INFRA. It provided information on the project, links to project tools and resources, activities and events, opportunities, and served to augment networking opportunities across the project. As well as directly hosting a wealth of dynamic content that constantly grew, it also linked to relevant content stored elsewhere, e.g. publications in repositories, databases, and archives, etc.

Deliverable	Target Outcome	Target
Research visits (Transnational Access Programme)	Yearly number of Fellows from M12-M48	O5.a: 7-9. Achieved, 50 fellows total, greater than 16/year. See below.
Forming institutional alliance for CLS	Number of institutions in alliance (M48)	O5.b: 14-15. Achieved, 14 institutions. See below.
Reporting on user needs beyond academia	Completion of report on user needs beyond academia (D3.5)	O5.c: 1 report, achieved with 4 infographics further communicated through videos, posters + website. See below.
Reporting on CLS training	Completion of final report on training events and materials, which includes an evaluative report produced following each training school (D4.2).	O5.d: Achieved, 3 reports included in final report. See below.
Reporting on TNA Programme	Completion of final report on TNA Programme, including process documentation and impact analysis (D9.1)	O5.e: 1 report. Achieved. See below.
Reporting on communication and dissemination	Completion of final report on dissemination, communication, and exploitation (D2.2)	O5.f: 1 report. Achieved. See below
Social media engagement	Number of followers / subscribers (M52)	O5.g: ≤ 2,000 (not satisfactory) ≥ 2,000 (satisfactory).
Website engagement	Creation of a dynamic website that serves as a hub of information for project members and target audiences. Measured by website analytics.	O5.h: ≤ 400 visits per month (not satisfactory) ≥ 400 visits per month (satisfactory) Not consistently achieved, but total of 832 Active users at CLSIINFRA.io. See Figure 3 for monthly visits.

Table 5: Objective 5

O5.a: Research visits (Transnational Access Programme)

- Raciti, Marco. "CLS INFRA D9.1 TNA Report, Including Process Documentation and Impact Analysis," August 28, 2025. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16983854>.

O5.b: Forming institutional alliance for CLS

- Institute of Polish Language at the Polish Academy of Sciences, Poland
- University of Potsdam, Germany
- Austrian Academy of Sciences, Austria

D2.2 Final Report on Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation

- National University of Distance Education, Spain
- École Normale Supérieure de Lyon, France
- Humboldt University of Berlin, German;
- Charles University, Czech Republic
- Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities, France
- Ghent Centre for Digital Humanities, Ghent University, Belgium
- Belgrade Centre for Digital Humanities, Serbia
- Huygens Institute for the History of the Netherlands (Royal Netherlands Academy of Arts and Sciences), Netherlands
- Trier Center for Digital Humanities, Trier University, Germany
- Moore Institute, National University of Ireland Galway, Ireland
- The Trinity Centre for Digital Humanities, Trinity College Dublin, Ireland

O5.c Reporting on user needs beyond academia

- Edmond, Jennifer, and Vera Yakupova. “CLS INFRA D3.5 User Needs Beyond Academic Research for Computational Literary Analysis,” August 30, 2024. <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.13605872>.
- Additional resources:
 - Yakupova, Vera, and Jennifer Edmond. “CLS INFRA T3.5 Interviews: Understanding User Requirements Beyond Academia.” Zenodo, July 22, 2024. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12784255>.
 - Hoover, Sarah. Beyond Academia: Uses of CLS Tools and Methods for Journalists, Policy Makers, GLAM and Medical Humanities. January 25, 2025. a4 x4. <https://zenodo.org/records/15212772>.
 - Video: Computational Literary Studies for Galleries, Libraries, Archives and Museums (GLAM). Beyond Academia Playlist, 2025. <https://youtu.be/xYQ1dkJMYfM>.
 - Video: Computational Literary Studies for Journalists. Beyond Academia Playlist, 2025. <https://youtu.be/NfhCD3qmPbU>.
 - Video: Computational Literary Studies for Medical Humanities. Beyond Academia Playlist, 2025. <https://youtu.be/EXAdSsrMujk>.
 - Video: Computational Literary Studies for Policy Makers. Beyond Academia Playlist, 2025. <https://youtu.be/mfp1nFmCTI8>.

O5.d Reporting on CLS training

D2.2 Final Report on Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation

- Buschenhenke, Floor, Anna Dijkstra, and Lisanne van Rossum. (2025). “CLS INFRA D4.2 Final report on training materials and events,” August 27, 2025. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16965727>, including reports on these training school events:
 - CLS INFRA Training School on Data and Annotation. Charles University, Prague, Czechia, 2022.
 - CLS INFRA Training School: Digging for Gold: Knowledge Extraction from Text. UNED, Madrid, Spain, 2023.
 - CLS INFRA Training School: ExploreCor - Using Programmable Corpora in Computational Literary Studies. ACDH-CH, Vienna, 2024.

O5.e Reporting on TNA Programme

- Raciti, Marco. “CLS INFRA D9.1 TNA Report, Including Process Documentation and Impact Analysis,” August 28, 2025. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16983854>.

O5.f Reporting on communication and dissemination

- CLS INFRA D2.2 Final Report on Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation

O5.g Social media engagement

- X: 956
- Mastodon: 286
- BlueSky: 300
- YouTube: 57
- Total: 1599

O5.h Website engagement

Figure 3: CLSinfra.io website users monthly count.

3.2. Overall Impact

CLS INFRA has been exceptionally well-positioned to deliver high impact results for the community of researchers, across sectors and interests, who use literary sources as a basis for their work. The project made the data, tools and knowledge for CLS easily and widely accessible in a coordinated and sustainable fashion; sharing standards and other drivers of efficiency and effectiveness across complementary data holders and developers; democratising and lowering the bar for digital approaches in this field, in particular for early career researchers; consolidating the research community; and exploring possible socio-economic benefits of enhanced and integrated access to digital and digitised literary texts.

Building upon the technical backbone, basic assets and experiences of a number of active, but disconnected, infrastructures and projects, CLS INFRA has integrated its results into the DARIAH ERIC in a way that was a guarantor of long-term sustainability. DARIAH ERIC, as full partner of the project, has used its extensive network and technical acumen not only to maintain the tools and services developed within the project, but also to meet the challenge of consolidating the community of literary studies and helping it fully embrace the digital as a mode of intellectual engagement with text. It is, therefore, to be expected that the ongoing post-project impact of CLS INFRA will be both technological and social: while the field of CLS is much smaller than that of literary studies in general, our activities aimed at expanding the user base and providing user-friendly tools and workflows have made CLS much easier to enter as a field, even for those researchers with little or no previous experiences in using digital tools.

The CLS INFRA project has a significant impact at **four levels of granularity**: that of the individual researcher, the institution, the research policy, and technology and innovation.

3.2.1. Individual Researcher

The primary stakeholders of the CLS INFRA Starting Community for CLS are the researcher users of infrastructures for the digitally-enabled investigation of literature and culture. We have optimised our consortium to deliver for this community in several ways:

Firstly, by bringing together key European as well as nationally-based infrastructures and services to further their development at European level, we ensure wider and easier access of the best research infrastructures in Europe to literary researchers, while also giving these institutions and projects the opportunity to draw in return on the diverse, humanities

research-led, results of the project generated by the CLS community. In this way, we have greatly expanded CLS researchers' access to and awareness of key resources available at a national level, but which may otherwise be hidden to potential users outside of the country where they were developed for reasons of visibility, language of interaction, or politics. Also, we have worked closely on the delivery of the project with the DARIAH ERIC, whose status and continuity will ensure that project results have a wide dissemination and reuse value. This is evidenced by the availability of training materials from the three CLS INFRA Training Schools on DARIAH CAMPUS and the reposting of social media posts including the CLS INFRA Newsletter by DARIAH EU.

Secondly, a significant theme within our development is a focus on bringing the “researchers to the tools and the data” physically and especially virtually. Our commitment to the development of accessible training materials and opportunities for learning and mentoring has aligned our activities to ensure that we are enabling skills development across the career stages and locations in which literary scholars beginning their engagement with the field of CLS, find themselves. This has allowed CLS INFRA to not only broaden its training and transnational access provision over the current baseline, but also to deepen its multiplying impact through nurturing a new generation of researchers.

Figure 4: Social media graphic on applicants to the second training school by location

Thirdly, our support for individual researchers in the time of the grant and beyond is the best that can be offered. The Transnational Access programme has given 50 researchers direct access to some of the highest performing facilities in Europe for CLS. The fact that we recruit strongly among non-established researchers (including early stage researchers, researchers in less digitally developed countries, and citizen scientists) through our social

media presence, newsletters, and invitations on mailing lists in multiple disciplines and countries, has increased the impact of these fellowships. Given this recruitment reach it is unsurprising that researchers from over 30 different countries have applied for fellowships. These researchers have formed an important part of the dissemination and communication strategy by creating and sharing research across our platforms and across a diverse range of CLS INFRA’s target communities. As an example, the following Mastodon post was favoured by former TNA applicants.

Figure 5: Mastodon post demonstrating links between former and future TNA Fellows

Finally, by involving representative researchers in the CLS community directly in the project team, we ensure adherence to a co-created user-centric approach in which real advances for the community can be facilitated by technical development in a rich context of interdisciplinary sharing of knowledge and techniques. As an example, the open-source collaboration platform used for our internal communications, Mattermost, lists 77 researchers and collaborators as members. Our network of projects and collaborators beyond the project team has been a significant asset in engaging, and extending, current accepted practices in the domain of CLS.

3.2.2. National/European Infrastructures and Research Institutions

As mentioned above, the CLS INFRA consortium draws its strength from the contributions of key national infrastructures and projects that have so far, for various reasons, achieved a somewhat limited scope or scale. By bringing our fourteen partners together for joint development toward mutually beneficial goals, CLS INFRA has fostered harmonisation of data and services across Europe, and reduced duplication in parallel national or project contexts. By facilitating sharing, CLS INFRA has also enabled countries with less well-developed national infrastructure to offer access to cutting edge services to their communities (which they would often not be able to invest in on their own) and enabled project-level services to achieve larger audiences and enhanced sustainability.

Knowledge based resources, both explicit (collections) and tacit (scientific information and processes that are documented, but almost infinitely adaptable) have been drawn together and integrated effectively for the good of the researchers, but also very much for their institutions. Being able to show a more direct link between their efforts to promote access to such knowledge and the impact it has on the knowledge generation processes of literary scholars, as this report accomplishes, is of great value, both in planning strategically for future developments, but also in making the case for their impact to external stakeholders and funders to provide cost effective, efficient investment with partners across Europe.

The CLS INFRA project provides these institutions with clear and actionable guidance regarding their user engagement directed toward the literary research community with its variety of deliverables. Through the CLS INFRA community and communication mechanisms, they have been not only supported in the improvement of their own services but also accessed a wider perspective on the research and researchers they support, the policies and practices that are emerging elsewhere in the system (such as open science and the EOSC), and the possible impact multipliers they may be able to access through the methodological and training initiatives CLS INFRA has developed and through specific software or processes that are openly available through the SSH Open Marketplace for Tools and Services.

In addition, for those institutions directly or indirectly involved in the training of researchers, CLS INFRA has provided a contextualised and robust set of materials they can use to develop their curricula or support independent learning for their local users, leading to better links between their skills provision and a growing user base of young and/or semi-professional literary scholars.

3.2.3. Research Policy

The impact of the CLS INFRA project at the level of research policy depends on five areas:

- Awareness of and satisfaction with CLS INFRA originating tools, services and initiatives;
- Strengthened culture of cooperation between institutional, national players and DARIAH;
- Increased diversity of European literary data resources openly accessible;
- Increased potential for international cooperation in literary research;
- Increased potential for cross-disciplinary research informed by easily accessible European literary data.

Facilitating Open Science (e.g. by investing into sustainable research infrastructures, providing for incentives to mobilise new user bases, or regulating for the integration of Open Science principles) is an important issue for EU policy-making. Focusing on literary research, CLS INFRA has made a contribution to informing respective policy discourses and evidence-based policymaking (see e.g. Lee & Kirkpatrick, 2006).

CLS and, indeed, the humanities in general remain highly marked by the atomised and heterogeneous nature of sources and methods, and the analogue workflows upon which so much of even digitally-enabled humanistic work relies (see e.g. Edmond and Garnett, 2015). As a result, it is not a surprise that reuse of research outputs, even high-profile, publicly available ones, has been generally low. By establishing both a modular, “tactical” (Sheratt, 2015) approach to infrastructure development (so as not to impact on aspects of a process where change is epistemically intrusive) and by placing an emphasis on ensuring an ecosystem by which to increase and harmonise the skills bases of the individual users, CLS INFRA has increased the possibility for reuse of its own results and, by example, of others in the wider ecosystem.

A goal of CLS INFRA was to produce policy and technology briefs for local, national and EU-level policy makers not only on the topic of sustainability of research results, but also, more generally, on the adoption of open science principles within humanities disciplines (an often challenging matching between emerging, STEM-driven policies, and the practices and values of humanities research communities). This goal has proved overly ambitious. Due to challenges such as lack of policy making expertise, capacity, and difficulty identifying channels with which to reach the target audience of policy makers, this goal was not realistic.

3.2.4. Technology Development and Innovation

CLS INFRA has also informed the emerging debate about cultural innovation (Pozzo, 2017), and how this can be better promoted, or, to turn the question around, how culturally informed perspectives can better inform technical developments, promoting new approaches inspired by challenging cultural content. Because CLS INFRA focuses on literary data and humanistic approaches, it has been able to reinforce some of the social and cultural aspects of technological adoption that engineering-led processes can sometimes obscure. Such advances were enabled by both the critical mass and advancement of both methods and researcher cultures within CLS INFRA. This is only a nascent conversation in the CLS community, but one which CLS INFRA has fostered and grown through its activities. In particular, the research that resulted in deliverables “[CLSIINFRA D8.3 Report on Applied NLP Named Entity Recognition](#)”, “[CLSIINFRA D8.4 Report on NLP Relational Extraction \(REX\)](#)” and “[CLSIINFRA D8.5 Report on Applied NLP Sentiment Analysis](#)” has fostered conversations about Large Language Models (LLMs) and Generative Artificial Intelligence (GenAI) at conferences and workshops during 2024 and 2025 that demonstrated the challenges, limits, and uses of these tools.

3.3. Dissemination Activity Impact

In order to create unified and easy access to the best European and national infrastructures for the CLS community which has not been fully supported to benefit from the existing infrastructures and data resources, CLS INFRA has:

- established and communicated current best practices in methods for the analysis of authorship, author gender, literary genre, and the canon in an interactive resource (“[CLSIINFRA D3.2 Series of Five Short Survey Papers on Methodological Issues](#)”);
- mapped, consolidated, and expanded the CLS community around current best practices with respect both to datasets and tools used and to methods of analysis employed by researchers in CLS;
- disseminated showcases (for the major literary genres covered) of successful applications of CLS methods to existing datasets which have been produced by infrastructures as well as in projects, by individual researchers and which are harmonised and federated by CLS INFRA;

- defined data sharing policies by creating robust documentation and guidelines around clearly defined workflows for producing, describing and annotating literary datasets in accordance with international standards and interoperable formats;
- organised outreach materials, seminars, training schools, and events in order to support new users in the CLS community to engage in dynamic knowledge exchange across national borders, which are about 1) harmonising access to resources by developing joint conceptual and metadata models for advanced data exchange, large-scale data mining and enhanced discoverability; and 2) preventing a duplication of services by fostering better coordination of activities between national and transnational efforts in the field of literary studies;
- strengthened the virtual CLS community by providing online training modules (e.g. on literary corpus curation, natural language processing for literary texts, or text mining for literary texts) as Open Education Resources (OER) via DARIAH-Campus, a discovery framework and hosting platform for Digital Humanities training materials;
- produced position papers on emerging trends driving innovation in CLS research;
- demonstrated the usefulness of the principles of the CLS INFRA ecosystem for applications beyond CLS and even beyond academia.

3.3.1. Communication and Dissemination Principles

A SWOT (strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats) analysis undertaken when developing “[CLSinfra D2.1 Communication and Dissemination Plan](#)” contextualised project communications within the field. A set of basic principles ensured that the project’s strengths and opportunities were rolled out during its evolution, whilst the above-mentioned weaknesses and threats were diminished, managed and faced with awareness.

- *Adaptability*: Given the scope of the project and the specific themes involved, the communication strategy needed to be comprehensive enough to cover the project as a whole, while being adaptable to other parties and stakeholder communities, which could benefit from the project discoveries, infrastructures and outcomes. E.g., specific channels were used to reach particular target groups, and dissemination materials were tailored to the needs of different end users.
- *Flexibility*: CLS INFRA’s communication through its distribution channels was flexible and open in order to create a responsive framework for being aware of

needs and challenges in its attempt to address audiences through its communication activities.

- *Dynamism*: Adaptability and flexibility combined to generate a dynamic element. A dynamic strategy was a key to maximise the impact of CLS INFRA.
- *Wording*: On the one hand, CLS INFRA speaks to academic users (researchers, students, etc.) in CLS fields as well as the field of Digital Humanities. On the other hand, it addresses cultural and heritage institutions (e.g. public libraries, museums, etc.), industry, and the public at large. Therefore, CLS INFRA followed a multi-layered communication strategy that uses accessible language with tailored messages (specialised, technical/linguistic vocabulary vs. jargon-free language) to speak to its varied audiences.
- *Integration*: A key aim of CLS INFRA is to integrate CLS methodologies, infrastructures, and resources across target communities. Our commitment to collaboration across communities and our open-access communication and dissemination commitment ensured that high levels of integration are achieved across and within target communities.

4. Impact assessment by audience group

The CLS INFRA project engaged a diverse range of stakeholders across academia, cultural heritage, policy, industry, and the public.³ Rather than addressing outputs by activity type as was done in “[CLS INFRA D2.1 Communication and Dissemination Plan](#)” (e.g. training, events, dissemination), this assessment focuses on the impact achieved for each target audience group, reflecting on outcomes, methods, and legacy. Each section provides an overview of the group, impact highlights, and the channels used to achieve that impact.

Evidence for the activities targeted to each of these groups is present throughout the CLS INFRA deliverables and communication materials outlined elsewhere in this report. This assessment, Section 4 of this report, draws on those materials to reflect on the work through the audience-focused lenses identified in “[CLS INFRA D2.1 Communication and Dissemination Plan](#)”. The section aims to demonstrate how durable, shareable, and reliable

³ The authors acknowledge the use of ChatGPT 4.0 to assist in restructuring a previous draft of this section into its current structure.

infrastructures were built, and how our multi-channel dissemination strategy ensured that each audience group could access and benefit from these outputs.

4.1. Academic Researchers

4.1.1. Overview

Academic researchers were the project's primary users, benefiting from access to tools, training, and a growing international CLS research community. They included computational literary scholars, traditional literary scholars, interdisciplinary researchers, and technical humanities scholars.

The infrastructural outputs of CLS INFRA will benefit this group during and after the project. Using the CLSINFRA.io website as a central repository, dissemination to this group focused on upgrading their CLS use, creating opportunities for collaboration, and providing training on new infrastructures.

4.1.2. Impact Highlights

- Bridged knowledge gaps between digital and analogue literary studies by offering accessible entry points into CLS.
- Facilitated adoption of CLS tools and methodologies through practical, hands-on workshops, training schools, and asynchronous online modules.
- Enabled scholarly exchange and methodological experimentation via TNA Fellowships and conferences.
- Provided opportunities for upskilling and engagement with cutting-edge research for both early-career and senior scholars.
- Strengthened cooperation networks within and beyond literary studies by fostering sustained partnerships and institutional engagement.

4.1.3. Key Channels & Activities

- CLS INFRA website, social media, mailing lists, and a regularly updated newsletter.

Peer-reviewed publications and presentations at key conferences. (See 8.1 Appendix 1: List of Scientific Journal Articles and 8.2 Appendix 2: Scientific Conference Papers / Posters).

- Transnational Access (TNA) Fellowships that allowed researchers to work with tools and expertise in partner institutions. (See “[CLSIINFRA D9.1 TNA Report, Including Process Documentation and Impact Analysis](#)”)
- Targeted online training materials and asynchronous learning opportunities. (See above, 3.1.4 Objective 5)
- Shared Zotero-based bibliography to connect community publications. (See https://www.zotero.org/groups/2908286/cls_infra_communication)
- YouTube tutorials and interviews that offered training and promoted researcher visibility. (See our [YouTube Channel](#) and videos on DARIAH CAMPUS contextualized by the materials and notebooks from each Training School: [Prague 2022](#), [Madrid 2023](#), and [Vienna 2024](#).)

4.2. Institutions (HEIs, Research Centres, GLAMs)

4.2.1. Overview

Higher education institutions, research centres, e-infrastructures, and cultural heritage institutions were both users and enablers of the project’s outputs. As partners or outreach targets, they were essential in mainstreaming and sustaining CLS practices.

4.2.2. Impact Highlights

- Strengthened institutional infrastructure for CLS through tailored messaging and integration of tools and methods into workflows.
- Promoted interdisciplinary collaboration between digital humanities units, broader humanities departments, and the GLAM (Galleries, Libraries, Archives, Museums) sector.
- Supported institutional policy development in line with best practices for open science, data sharing, and interdisciplinary research.
- Fostered long-term integration and sustainability of CLS outputs beyond the project lifetime through institutional partnerships.

4.2.3. Key Channels & Activities

- Direct outreach, community building, and shared infrastructure development. (See “[CLSIINFRA D1.2: Strategic Roadmap for Computational Literary Studies](#)” and

[“CLSI INFRA D5.3 Toolkit Report for Data Sharing between Researchers and Institutions”](#))

- Mailing lists, infographics, reports, and internal communications platforms (e.g. Mattermost, NextCloud).
- Participation in joint events, training schools, and research exchange programmes.
- Co-creation of data sharing policies and dissemination of strategic outputs through institutional channels.

4.3. Policy Makers

4.3.1. Overview

European and national policy actors in research, innovation, education, and open science were engaged to ensure alignment of CLSI INFRA outcomes with policy frameworks. These included national research agencies, EU-level institutions, MEPs, and advocacy bodies. Attracting a policy-maker audience proved a difficult challenge. As expressed in [“CLSI INFRA D3.5 User Needs Beyond Academic Research for Computational Literary Analysis”](#), the capacity of audience this audience to develop connections and understanding is under high time pressure. Thus the poster, video and webpage using infographics formatting responds to the needs of this audience, as does the template-formatted Policy Brief.

4.3.2. Impact Highlights

- Contributed to policy discourse on open science, research infrastructure sustainability, and humanities research impact.
- Produced targeted policy and technology communications valorise research outcomes clearly and concisely.
- Ensured that the value and relevance of CLSI infrastructures were made visible within existing and emerging policy frameworks.
- Created clear calls to action and evidence-based recommendations for policy makers invested in digital humanities.

4.3.3. Key Channels & Activities

- Development and dissemination of policy briefs, white papers, and reports.
- Strategic stakeholder mapping and use of personal contact networks.

- Participation in advisory boards and high-level dissemination events.
- Use of infographics, explanatory videos, and concise materials tailored to policymaker communication preferences.

4.4. Industry (Tech, Creative, Cultural Sectors)

4.4.1. Overview

The project reached out to industries intersecting with culture, technology, education, and journalism. These partners represented non-academic but influential vectors for the use and dissemination of CLS outputs.

4.4.2. Impact Highlights

- Promoted the reuse and adaptation of CLS methods and tools within commercial and public-facing sectors.
- Facilitated professional upskilling through training activities and easily accessible learning materials.
- Created space for dialogue between academic research and real-world applications in heritage, journalism, and tourism.
- Raised awareness of how digital literary methods could be applied to storytelling, public history, and data analysis in non-academic settings.

4.4.3. Key Channels & Activities

- Production of infographics and promotional brochures specifically for non-academic audiences.
- Direct outreach through creative sector mailing lists and community events.
- Co-hosted workshops and events that encouraged sector-specific engagement.
- Dissemination of accessible training outputs via social media, YouTube, and project website.

4.5. Citizens and Other Kinds of Researchers

4.5.1. Overview

Life-long learners, educators, journalists, genealogists, and citizen scientists were considered essential to the democratisation and dissemination of CLS tools and knowledge. This group included non-academic researchers and members of the public interested in literary data.

4.5.2. Impact Highlights

- Made literary data and tools openly accessible, empowering self-guided exploration and informal learning.
- Created opportunities for public engagement and lifelong learning beyond traditional academic pathways.
- Amplified outreach through collaborations with stakeholders who served as intermediaries to public networks.
- Built lasting engagement through accessible and clearly explained resources that removed barriers to participation.

4.5.3. Key Channels & Activities

- Social media campaigns and outreach via newsletters.
- Mass media communication and event-based public engagement.
- YouTube tutorials, TNA fellow videos, and project explainers.
- Dedicated public sections on the project website and downloadable resources.

4.6. Summary

By focusing on impact per audience group, CLS INFRA ensured that its outputs were not only disseminated but integrated and sustained across sectors. Its multi-layered approach allowed for long-lasting, audience-specific transformation in knowledge, skills, and infrastructure access. The lasting presence of its website and materials guarantees continued engagement across academic, public, and policy communities.

This audience-specific strategy reflects the project's understanding that infrastructure development is not merely technical but fundamentally social. Through trust-building, collaboration, and clearly targeted messaging, CLS INFRA has contributed to a more inclusive, connected, and forward-looking research ecosystem.

5. Communication Channel Details

5.1. Communication Channel Overview

As each project partner is committed to create a high level of publicity for the project right from the beginning, the launch and objectives of CLS INFRA were communicated through partners' communication channels (e.g. press releases, newsletters, news-related media, website, social media etc.) to generate broad public awareness of CLS INFRA activities.

Nevertheless, CLS INFRA also established its own communication channels, to bundle partner activities and produce its own output, whilst *collaborating* with its partners to foster community building by generating awareness (online and offline) and stimulate participation.

CLS INFRA counted on a variety of available (communication) channels and resources that are managed either by CLS INFRA, CLS INFRA Consortium partners or third parties. It is important not only that we used our own channels and resources but also third party channels in order to raise the project's reach.

Section 5 of this report discusses the content of public and internal communications and dissemination activities.

5.2. Internal Communications

Mattermost (an open source collaboration platform) was CLS INFRA's main internal communication platform (access to our communication channels restricted to group members). This platform allows for secure, quick, and intuitive communications across WPs, members, and project activities and aligns with the project's commitment to open source technology and resources. Email was still used to duplicate some Mattermost posts to those who prefer a single contact source for their communications.

NextCloud was the project’s platform for sharing internal documents and files. It is available to the consortium and associated partners and to the European Commission. This platform will be permanently updated and improved in line with the project results. NextCloud is also an open source platform and continues our commitment to open source technology and resources.

IJP-PAN was the host for both of these platforms.

In 2024 we developed an internal communications survey, as the disruption of the pandemic makes such review of primary importance. At that time, responses were minimal (8% of the project team members). Therefore, we repeated the survey in February 2025 and reached a combined 25% response rate. In the survey we evaluated the forms of communication most used and most useful, and the perspective of team members on how strong internal communications are and how well they have functioned. The findings indicate that beginning the project during the COVID-19 pandemic increased the difficulty of developing good internal communications patterns and trust in both one’s work package team and other work package teams, largely due to the lack of face-to-face meeting and socialisation available. A summary of these findings are found in 8.4 Appendix 4: Internal Communications Survey Results.

Figure 6: effectiveness of internal communications channels

5.3. Email

An email-address (info@clsinfra.io) was set up which was used for sending out newsletters and mailing lists, the contact form on the website, and on social media channels in their contact section, to enable the interested user to ask questions or send feedback.

5.4. Social media

The main goal of using social media is to significantly expand CLS INFRA's organic reach, as well as to keep each account up to date by curating continuous postings and shares on a regular basis. A key strength of the CLS INFRA proposal is its commitment to create a critical mass of coordinated key infrastructure partners, but also to build on current and past initiatives and projects. As a result of this, we were able to use our social media channels to forge connections and links to these partners through a discursive output and increase our reach through their follow bases. In particular, Twitter/X, Mastodon@fedihum server, and BlueSky were the main social media channels of communication. Their "thread" structure is useful in collecting and collating groups of publications, videos, resources, and events, and the "pinned" section was kept up to date with the latest project events and activities. Before 2023, Twitter/X was the main social media channel. In 2022/2023, changes to the structure and management functions of Twitter/X lessened its efficacy. To broaden our discursive community, WP2 also posted to a targeted CLS and GLAM audience from the Mastodon@fedihum server and the Digital Humanities community on BlueSky.

CLS INFRA's social media leveraged connections with partner channels and third party channels to raise the project's reach (see "[CLS INFRA D2.1 Communication and Dissemination Plan](#)" for lists of partner and third-party channels). Communications staff then posted regularly and strategically followed other users, and re-posted important announcements such as conference CFPs, job and funding opportunities, or major policy decisions related to institutions specialising in digital humanities and computational literary or linguistic analysis. On BlueSky, a Starter Pack highlighting individuals, institutions, and organisations focused on CLS deepened these connections and broadened the audience involved in this important conversation.

5.5. Website

The project website served as a central access point for information on CLS INFRA, its background, aims, and results, as well as providing an access point for its tools, services, and data. The following pages and sections serve as examples of these goals.

- [Events](#): An overview of upcoming CLS INFRA events were hosted on the “Events” section of the site, informing interested users of event details and providing them with information on how to register for and attend these events. The “Events” section of the site also archived information including video recordings and publications emerging from past events to serve as an informative archiving of the project events and associated materials.
- [Project Outputs](#): This chronological set of output summaries identified and linked to each deliverable, explainer, TNA interview, or other output from the project. Repositories, publications and other outputs were made explicit through linked buttons. A table of contents encouraged identification of similar outputs.
- [Library](#): This page featured an embedded ZotPress Bibliography, a Zotero-based plugin that updated from the CLS INFRA Zotero Group. This allowed the project team members to update their publications, datasets and other outputs in both places simultaneously.
- [TNA Archive](#): This section hosted the full report from each TNA Fellow’s experience along with any recordings of presentations or links to publications related to their work as TNA fellows.

D2.2 Final Report on Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation

Other pages, including “[Infographics: Beyond Academia](#)”, “[D3.2: Survey of Methods](#)” and “[D5.3: Toolkit for Data Sharing](#)” offered useful advice in easy-to-understand interactive methods such as a wiki or a clickable grid.

Home » Resources » D3.2: Survey of Methods

CLSIINFRA COMPUTATIONAL LITERARY STUDIES INFRASTRUCTURE

Home About Resources Opportunities Events News CONTACT

D3.2: Survey of Methods

Survey Grid

This survey documents current, widespread practices in research areas or issues that are prominent within CLS.

Click on a heading below to read an overview of terms and literature.

	General Remarks	Authorship Attribution	Genre Analysis	Literary History	Gender	Canonicity / Prestige
General Remarks	General Introduction	What is Authorship Attribution?	What is Genre Analysis?	What is Literary History?	What is Gender Analysis?	What is Canonicity?
Corpus Building	Introduction to Corpus Building	Corpus Building for Authorship Attribution	Corpus Building for Genre Analysis	Corpus Building for Literary History	Corpus Building for Gender Analysis	Corpus Building for Canonicity
Preprocessing and Annotation	Introduction to Preprocessing and Annotation	Annotation for Authorship Attribution	Annotation for Genre Analysis	Annotation for Literary History	Annotation for Gender Analysis	Annotation for Canonicity
Data Analysis	Introduction to Data Analysis	Analysis in Authorship Attribution	Data Analysis for Genre	Analysis in Literary History	Analysis for Gender	Analysis of Canonicity
Evaluation	Introduction to Evaluation	Evaluation in Authorship Attribution	Evaluation in Genre Analysis	Evaluation in Literary History	Evaluation for Gender Analysis	Evaluation for Canonicity

Additional resources: [FULL PDF](#) [FRONT MATTER](#) [REFERENCES](#) [POST SCRIPTUM](#)

Citation suggestion

Each section of the Survey includes a citation suggestion relevant to that section.
To cite the whole:

Christof Schöch, Julia Dudak, Evgeniia Fileva, eds. (2023). Survey of Methods in Computational Literary Studies (= CLS INFRA D3.2: Series of Five Short Survey Papers on Methodological Issues). With contributions by Joanna Byszuk, Julia Dudak, Evgeniia Fileva, Andressa Gomide, Lisanne van Rossum, Christof Schöch, Artjoms Šeja and Karina van Dalen-Oskam. Version 1.1.0, May 5, 2023. Trier: CLS INFRA. URL: <https://methods.clsinfra.io>, DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7892112.

16 Views: 16

Home About Resources Opportunities Events News

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101004984

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Figure 7: Example of website, interactive survey grid

The website also linked partner and third-party websites to cement connections between partner institutions and third-party channels (see “[CLS INFRA D2.1 Communication and Dissemination Plan](#)” for lists).

The project website will be maintained as a static resource for at least five years after the close of the project, at which point it will be folded into the DARIAH Literary Studies Domain Centre. The website was built using a well-known modular web content manager system (Wordpress), which allows the pages to be fully responsive on all devices (desktop, tablet, and smartphone) and browsers.

5.6. YouTube

A [YouTube channel](#) was set up, providing users with 98 informative videos, e.g. tutorials and training materials on how to use the provided infrastructure, recordings of online or hybrid events, infographic videos, and interview material with group members, partners, and collaborators. This material was shared across our social media platforms, in newsletters, and embedded into our website.

In addition, editing services provided by WP2 and links from repositories of materials such as DARIAH-CAMPUS to the CLS INFRA YouTube channel ensured that branding is consistent across all outputs.

Figure 8: Example of thumbnail for TNA Fellowship video

5.7. Infographics

Each infographic exists as a webpage and social media-appropriate video as well as A4 posters distributed at conferences and over mailing list channels. Each outlines the specific needs of a target area (GLAM, Medical Humanities, Policy Makers and Journalists), provides an example (posters) or two (videos, webpages) of a tool and what kinds of question it might answer, and acknowledges the challenges that might be faced by citizen scientists in that area. All infographics are designed to direct traffic to the resources on the CLS INFRA webpage. See 8.5 Appendix 5: Infographics for details.

</> CLS INFRA
 COMPUTATIONAL LITERARY STUDIES INFRASTRUCTURE

The power of storytelling for Journalists

CLS Tools and methods

Attention is valuable.

Leveraging fiction and the tools of CLS can provide creative inspiration, better narrative building, and connection to your audience.

Example: Emotions of London

Algorithmically analyse large collections of text to create visuals that show patterns such as the incidence of place names over time. Show the connection between literary narratives and contemporary issues.

See The Emotions of London project, Stanford Literary Lab (litlab.stanford.edu)

CLS INFRA has identified ways to use literature in journalism based on interviews with journalists.

Find the report*, interviews, video explainers and more resources:
clsinfra.io/resources/beyond-academia

*D3.5: Understanding User Requirements beyond Academic Research, 2024.

 Computational Literary Studies Infrastructure (CLS INFRA) has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101004984.

Figure 9: Poster version of the Journalism Infographic. Also available as webpage and video explainer.

5.8. Mailing Lists

WP2 personnel maintained and updated a curated roster of mailing lists where announcements of events, new resources, public presentations, and newsletter publications could be posted. These were curated toward the appropriate audiences as identified in section 4 of this report. E.g., all information would be sent to eadh-topics@lists.digitalhumanities.org, while the GLAM Wikimedia mailing list was used to communicate explainers, infographics, and other materials meeting the impact goals of CLS INFRA towards its institutional audience.

5.9. Newsletter

A database of up-to-date contacts was developed in order to reach the largest audience possible, who were regularly updated using a (GDPR compliant) mass mailing online tool, Mailchimp.

As CLS INFRA members were present at (project relevant) events, interested recipients were invited to subscribe to the CLS INFRA mailing list and there was a subscribe button on the project website. At the close of the project the MailChimp audience had grown from 80 in its initial database to 481 subscribers.

A newsletter template was set up according to the CLS INFRA corporate identity guidelines; subscribers were updated regularly, filtered by audience (e.g.: early career researchers, citizen scientists, heritage groups, etc.). 8.6 Appendix 6: Newsletter Sample for an example.

Figure 10: CLS INFRA newsletter engagements by issue

5.10. Events

Organising, promoting and attending events fosters the community, supports networking with other initiatives/infrastructures, and creates an opportunity to engage with academia, heritage and cultural groups, and the general public. Furthermore, it generates dissemination output (e.g. papers in conference proceedings).

These events were significant reputation-builders across a variety of our audiences. These events were focused, but also highly interactive, harnessing formats like the world café and the rapid ideation session where appropriate. They were recorded and promoted on the CLS INFRA website, to increase their impact.

Information on upcoming CLS INFRA events were publicised on our website and outputs from those events were hosted and promoted through our website and social media platforms. Recordings (where applicable) and outcomes from past events were also archived on our website in the Project Outputs page so that users can engage with the project's activities and events at any stage. Project members could promote and add event information and outputs through the established WP2 communication channels.

During current global restrictions related to the ongoing COVID-19 pandemic, it was important to have a strategy for engaging the desired CLS INFRA communities using accessible digital technologies. As such, CLS INFRA was dedicated to an open, accessible, and, where possible, hybrid approach, which ensured that the widest cohort of our target communities can access our events and activities. Online video platforms such as Zoom and Teams were an important tool for our online events, both during the pandemic and in the changed digital culture following it. We also (where appropriate) recorded or archived events and activities to ensure accessibility across communities.

5.10.1. CLS INFRA Events

A kick-off meeting took place on March 15th 2021 and another public-facing meeting was be organised for early 2022, taking place in the first year of the project. In the second, third and fourth year of the project, CLS community-fostering events, such as training schools, were initiated in order to strengthen the community by encouraging personal contact. The nature of these events was influenced by ongoing COVID-19 travel restrictions, hence the 100+ participants online at the Training School in 2023 in Madrid, and all consortium members

adhered to local guidelines for travel. A Wrap-Up event held in Krakow in July of 2025 was attended by 17 project team members and 29 additional community members.

5.10.2. CLS INFRA Training Measures

CLS INFRA offered both face-to-face and asynchronous training materials (modelled after the units of the PARTHENOS Training Suite, see: <https://training.parthenos-project.eu/> and hosted on DARIAH-Campus, <https://campus.dariah.eu/>), adaptable to the level and specific needs of a large number of new and semi-established users of CLS methods. In addition, the Transnational Access Fellowships allowed intermediate users to make significant progress on their own specific projects, working in situ with the assets and expertise of their host institutions.

5.10.3. CLS INFRA TNA Fellowships

The Trans National Access Programme facilitated the invitation of scholars to visit consortium institutions for a spell of 1-3 months to work on tasks or projects related to CLS INFRA. A call for Transnational Access Fellows was made six times during the project and an advisory board appointed to decide on the successful applicants. 50 fellowships took place between M8 and M48. WP2 utilised these opportunities for dissemination, communication, and impact by spotlighting these Fellows on our website and YouTube as well as in other relevant communications materials. As well as this, each Fellow contributed a short blog post, report, video, presentation, publication or social media output during their time in role in order to disseminate their research and training experience. A [TNA Archive](#) containing this material on the CLS INFRA website was completed in 2023. 37 videos have been completed and [can be found on this playlist](#).

Institutional partners fostered community and education by hosting TNA Fellow presentations and TNA mini-conferences at the University of Galway, ACHDH-OEAW, TCDH, LINHD-UNED, and Ghent CDH. Audiences to these were either invited members of the institution, in the case of ACHDH-OEAW or public. If public, these were recorded and publicised on the website, in newsletters, to mailing lists, and on social media.

TNA Fellows' communication about their own work and the resources of CLS INFRA exemplifies the ecosystem reach of the project through forming strong networks.

Figure 11: BlueSky post by Agnieszka Szulińska, a CLS INFRA TNA Fellow

5.10.4. Third-party events

Dissemination was carried out at third party events or joint events (e.g. workshops, conferences, panels, presence at other international or national events) in order to reach out to other communities and enlarge the community of interest. Individual researchers or research groups participated with posters, panels, or presentations and presented specific

project results. Presentations at these events are listed in 8.2 Appendix 2: Scientific Conference Papers / Posters. These achieved recognition as important contributions to the CLS field and beyond. (See Table 6.)

Reviews of abstract for paper accepted to UK / IE DH 2025.	
Title: "Collaborative Infrastructures for Multilingual Digital Literary Studies: CLS INFRA"	
<i>Score</i>	<i>Text</i>
3 (Strong accept)	The CLS INFRA project has been a landmark event in DH around the world. I think the conference and its theme suits the presentation perfectly.
2 (Accept)	This poster proposal showcases the work of the CLS INFRA initiative at the late stages of its development. Beyond the collaborative aspect of the project, its multilingual, multiplatform and multiformat capabilities makes the project very relevant to the event's audiences.

Table 6: Showing reviewer comments on conference abstract

CLS INFRA partnered with ADHO SIG-DLS at DH2024 and DH2025 to lead full-day mini-conferences. In 2024, in Arlington, Virginia, USA, 35 attendees discussed the theme "Computational Literary Studies: How To Do Research Responsibly", while in 2025, in Lisbon, Portugal, 90 attendees discussed "Comparative Literature Goes Digital".

5.11. Dissemination Material

The dissemination material distributed followed the corporate design guidelines described below. Distribution items included downloadable posters based on the Infographics targeted toward Medical Humanities, Journalism, Policy-Making and GLAM, t-shirts, badges / lapel

Figure 12: ISTR2025 Conference attendee Siobhán O'Gorman, winner of a CLS INFRA T-shirt. Shown holding CLS INFRA notebook. Photo credit: Sarah Hoover.

pins, pencils, notebooks, recycled bamboo charging pads, cable managers, and stickers. These were distributed at every training school and all events attended by WP2 personnel as well as third party events and conferences such as DHBenelux and the Conference of Computational Literary Studies (CCLS) .

5.12. Logo and Visual Style

The CLS INFRA logos were created by Allen Creative Ltd. for CLS INFRA and were the starting point for creating a visual style for the project. Within CLS INFRA, we used typography to sustain our image and identity across all communication channels and publications. Our logos were downloadable from our website so that participants in any CLS INFRA programme could remain consistent in their own presentations and publications. Refer to [“CLS INFRA D2.1 Communication and Dissemination Plan”](#) for details, or see 8.7 Appendix 7: Project Summary Posters for posters designed yearly, a sample of consistent aesthetic design with variations.

5.13. Online Promotion Material

Digital and online marketing activities were undertaken, which will be styled and branded in relation to the guidelines listed above. These activities included:

- Regular news items in the CLS INFRA newsletter, linked to the CLS INFRA website;
- Regular social media posts on our social media channels (Twitter/X, Mastodon, YouTube) by the project on the CLS INFRA account and by the Consortium members on their institutional accounts or private accounts, including videos, pictures, figures, photos, tables, etc.
- As videos are the most shared content on the web, self-produced videos were shared and posted on social media (Twitter/X, YouTube); those videos will provided information about the deployment of the infrastructure, mini-interviews with experts from the field, mini- tutorials, as well as hints & tips videos for usability in various scenarios;
- Pictures, photo material, interactive tools, a library collection, and graphics representative for the project were generated and distributed through the project's channels, primarily through NextCloud.

5.14. Offline Promotion Material

The majority of our promotional materials were digital, however CLS INFRA also utilised print publicity, where appropriate, to maximise the impact of the dissemination activity and to establish an initial contact with organisations where digital marketing proves unsuccessful.

Relevant leaflets, flyers, posters, and other materials were produced with an option for physical printing in mind and we also make use of tangible merchandise as noted above.

Print materials were available for download from relevant pages of the website (e.g. general info brochure, topic specific one-page inserts, flyers, posters).

5.15. Scientific Dissemination

Papers and articles about the project results were published in open access journals and conferences. The online repository *Zenodo* was used to preserve peer-reviewed scientific papers and other research materials published by CLS INFRA partners in a [Zenodo Community](#).

In 2023, [an interactive grid tool](#) based on “[CLS INFRA D3.2 Series of Five Short Survey Papers on Methodological Issues](#)” was published on the CLS INFRA website, linking to the published papers on *Zenodo*. Similarly, in 2024 a [Toolkit for Data Sharing](#) based on “[CLS INFRA D5.3 Toolkit Report for Data Sharing Between Researchers and Institutions in the Field of Literary Studies](#)” and a [Library](#) (linked to the Zotero CLS INFRA group) were published there. In 2025, [the infographics](#) developed from “[CLS INFRA D3.5 User Needs Beyond Academic Research for Computational Literary Analysis](#)” added downloadable posters, videos and visual content.

In particular, we ensured where possible project outputs are available via “green” open access, either through the repositories of one of the project partners or through the DARIAH shared resource repository, HAL. Green Open Access is the norm for humanities publishing but does require educated choices regarding target journals so as to avoid undue delays due to embargos. The leadership of WP2 considered this issue carefully in consultation with project colleagues. Where open access publication was not possible, project members committed to putting appropriate drafts or pre-publication materials on *Zenodo* or on the e-Print archive <https://arxiv.org/>. In almost all cases a *Zenodo* publication ensured green-level open access.

6. Evaluation, Monitoring and Reporting

The impact created through the innovations implemented in the creation of CLS infrastructures were measured, as well as the data gathered from training measures (number of participants, etc.). Such measurements appear throughout this report, along with measurements of outreach and engagement with the help of the reporting system of the mass mailing tool, with website analytics (Mailchimp, Wordpress) and with the standard reporting features of social media portals and the figures/data collected at events.

Our communication and dissemination strategy was kept updated regularly in line with our monitoring and evaluation procedures, with a complete revision in 2023 to v2 of “[CLSI INFRA D2.1 Communication and Dissemination Plan](#)”. This final communication report (M52) thus contains summative reflections on communication and dissemination activities, and as planned also include scientific publications and a collection of digital and non-digital media clippings.

7. References

Edmond J., and Victoria Jane Garnett (2015) “APIs and Big Data: the Emperor’s New Clothes.” *International Journal for Digital Curation*. Vol. 10.1, pp. 287-297.

Lee, N., and C. Kirkpatrick (2006). Evidence-based policy-making in Europe: An evaluation of European Commission integrated impact assessments. *Impact Assessment and Project Appraisal* 24(1): 23-33. <https://doi.org/10.3152/147154606781765327>

Pozzo, Riccardo, and Vania Virgili (2017) “Social and Cultural Innovation: Research Infrastructures Tackling Migration.” *Diogenes*, November 6, 2017, 0392192117739822. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0392192117739822>.

Sherratt, T. (2015) “Towards A Manifesto for Tactical DH Research Infrastructure.” YouTube, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=FL5pP2ysjU4>.

8. Appendices

8.1. Appendix 1: List of Scientific Journal Articles

Benito-Santos, Alejandro, Adrián Ghajari, Pedro Hernández, Víctor Fresno Fernández, Salvador Ros, Elena González-Blanco García, Alejandro Benito-Santos, et al.

“LyricSIM: Un nuevo dataset y benchmark para la detección de similitud en letras de canciones en español.” *Procesamiento del lenguaje natural* 71 (2023): 149–63.

Benito-Santos, Alejandro, Salvador Muñoz, Roberto Sánchez Therón, and Franciso J García Peñalvo. “Characterizing the Visualization Design Space of Distant and Close Reading of Poetic Rhythm.” *Frontiers in Big Data* 6, no. 1 (2023): 1167708.

Fritsche, Katrin, and Sander Münster. “Taking up Artificial Intelligence as Teaching and Learning Content in the Digital Humanities – Topics, Categorisations, and Examples.” *Proceedings of The International Conference on Advanced Research in Teaching and Education* 1, no. 1 (June 9, 2024): 8–24. <https://doi.org/10.33422/icate.v1i1.225>.

Ghajari, Adrián, Salvador Ros, and Álvaro Pérez. “Querying the Depths: Unveiling the Strengths and Struggles of Large Language Models in SPARQL Generation.” *Procesamiento del Lenguaje Natural* 73 (September 2024): 271–81.

Mikołajec, Marek Jan. “Sztuczna Inteligencja w Świetle Humanistyki Cyfrowej i Literaturoznawstwa.” *Media i Społeczeństwo. Medioznawstwo, Komunikologia, Semiologia, Socjologia Mediów* 20 (2024): 185–99.

Pérez Pozo, Álvaro, Javier de la Rosa, Salvador Ros, Elena González-Blanco, Laura Hernández, and Mirella de Sisto. “A Bridge Too Far for Artificial Intelligence?: Automatic Classification of Stanzas in Spanish Poetry.” *Journal of the Association for Information Science and Technology* 73, no. 2 (2022): 258–67. <https://doi.org/10.1002/asi.24532>.

8.2. Appendix 2: Scientific Conference Papers / Posters

Bekius, Lamyk, Floor Buschenhenke, Karina van Dalen-Oskam, Maciej Eder, Michaela Mahlberg, Bas Groes, Artjoms Šeļa, and Martin Wynne. “Computational Literary Studies UK Training School.” Training School, University of Wolverhampton, UK, May

- 14, 2024. <https://www.wlv.ac.uk/research/research-centres/ctr---centre-for-transnational-and-transcultural-research/clsuk/>.
- Birkholz, Julie, Ingo Börner, Sally Chambers, Vera Charvat, Silvie Cinková, Tess Dejaeghere, Julia Dudar, et al. "Computational Literary Studies Infrastructure (CLS INFRA): A Project to Connect People, Data, Tools, and Methods." Tokyo, Japan, 2022. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7040158>.
- Birkholz, Julie M. "Digital Tools and DH Support (GhentCDH)." Study Morning presented at the MAPS - the UGent periodical studies research group study day on digitization, University of Ghent, March 15, 2024. <https://event.ugent.be/registration/event/1ad43f5a-2f28-4d32-9b7a-be01ce3e788c>.
- Birkholz, Julie M., Ingo Börner, Floor Buschenhenke, Byszuk, Joanna, Sally Chambers, Vera Maria Charvat, Silvie Cinková, et al. "CLS INFRA: Leveraging Literary Methods for FAIR(Er) Science." In *DH2025*. Lisbon, Portugal, 2025.
- . "Poster: Collaborative Infrastructures for Multilingual Digital Literary Studies: CLS INFRA." Glasgow, UK, 2025.
- Birkholz, Julie M., Ingo Börner, Joanna Byszuk, Sally Chambers, Vera Charvat, Silvie Cinková, Tess Dejaeghere, et al. "Literary Methods for All: CLS INFRA 2024 Poster." Leuven: Zenodo, 2024. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.12742275>.
- Birkholz, Julie M., Ingo Börner, Joanna Byszuk, Sally Chambers, Vera Maria Charvat, Silvie Cinková, Tess Dejaeghere, et al. "Computational Literary Studies Infrastructure (CLS INFRA): Initial Findings and Conclusions for the Field: Literature by Numbers." In *Digital Humanities 2023: Book of Abstracts*, 497–98. Graz, Austria: Zenodo, 2023. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.8107903>.
- Birkholz, Julie M., Ingo Börner, Sally Chambers, Silvie Cinková, Karina Van Dalen-Oskam, Tess Dejaeghere, Dudar, Julia, et al. "Computational Literary Studies Infrastructure (CLSINFRA): A H2020 Research Infrastructure Project That Aids to Connect Researchers, Data, and Methods." In *DHBenelux 2022*. Eshsur-Alzette, Luxembourg, 2022. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6573892>.
- Börner, Ingo, Vera Maria Charvát, Matej Ďurčo, Adrián Ghajari, Lukas Plank, and Salvador Ros. "Consolidating the Heterogeneous Landscape of Literary Corpora." In *DARIAH*

Annual Event 2024 Proceedings. NOVA, Lisbon, Portugal, 2024.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.12807802>.

Börner, Ingo, Vera Maria Charvat, Matej Ďurčo, Sabine Laszakovits, Michał Mrugalski, and Stefan Resch. “Enhancing Findability and Accessibility of Poetry Resources in Multi-Genre Collections across Different Languages.” In *Digital Humanities 2023: Book of Abstracts*, 125–27. Graz, Austria, 2023. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.7961822>.

Börner, Ingo, Vera Maria Charvat, Matej Ďurčo, Michał Mrugalski, and Carolin Odebrecht. “Computational Literary Studies Data Landscape Review.” In *DHd 2022: Kulturen des digitalen Gedächtnisses*. Potsdam: Universität Potsdam, 2022. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.6327952>.

Börner, Ingo, Charvat, Vera Maria, Ďurčo, Matej, Mrugalski, Michał, and Odebrecht, Carolin. “Computational Literary Studies Data Landscape Review.” In *DHd 2022: Kulturen Des Digitalen Gedächtnisses*, 272–73. Potsdam: Universität Potsdam, 2022. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.6322462>.

Börner, Ingo, Frank Fischer, Carsten Milling, and Henny Sluyter-Gäthje. “Einführung in DraCor - Programmable Corpora Für Die Digitale Dramenanalyse.” In *DHd 2022: Kulturen Des Digitalen Gedächtnisses*. Potsdam: Universität Potsdam, 2022.

Börner, Ingo, Peer Trilcke, Carsten Milling, Frank Fischer, and Henny Sluyter-Gäthje. “Dockerizing DraCor – A Container-Based Approach to Reproducibility in Computational Literary Studies.” In *Digital Humanities 2023: Book of Abstracts*, 293–95. Graz, Austria, 2023. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8107835>.

Burnard, Lou, Peer Trilcke, and Maciej Eder. “Introduction and Discussion of Core Technologies and Projects.” Workshop, Online, September 21, 2021.

Calvo Tello, José, Nanette Reißler-Pipka, Sally Chambers, Philippe Genêt, and Patrick Helling. “Metadata Desiderata for Literary Corpora: A Survey for Starting a Conversation between Literary Studies, Libraries and Research Data Repositories.” In *DH2024*. George Washington University, VA, USA: Zenodo, 2024. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.11202131>.

Ceresato, Floriana. “TNA Seminar: Digital Humanities and Medieval Romance Philology: Two Case Studies.” University of Galway, Ireland, July 3, 2024. <https://youtu.be/fzmFjel3FK4>.

- Cinková, Silvie, Václav Cvrček, Maarten Janssen, and Michal Křen. “How Corpus Analysis Helps Operationalize Research Questions and Entices Literary Scholars to Learn Programming.” In *Digital Humanities 2023: Book of Abstracts*, 323–25. Graz, Austria: [object Object], 2023. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.8107803>.
- Cinková, Silvie, and Maarten Janssen. “Towards a Sustainable Community Effort: Training NLP Data for under-Resourced Language Domains in CLS.” In *TwinTalks 4: Understanding and Facilitating Remote Collaboration in Digital Humanities*. Graz, 2023.
- Dalen-Oskam, Karina van, Bas Groes, Aidan Byrne, Peter Harvey, Adrian Leguina, Tom Mercer, and Demi-Mae Wilton. “Comparing Perceptions of Literary Quality.” In *Digital Humanities 2023*. Graz, Austria: Zenodo, 2023. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.8107953>.
- Deijl, Lucas van der. “Building DutchDraCor: Comparative Perspectives on Early Modern Dutch Drama in European Context.” University of Potsdam, April 24, 2024.
- Dejaeghere, Tess. “Beyond Babylonian Confusion: A Case-Study Based Approach for Multilingual Nlp on Historical Literature,” 1, 2022. https://drive.google.com/file/d/14Ump5sqJKsDv_Doc6xc0J7LloNCF82t5/view?usp=sharing.
- . “Data-Driven Approaches to Ancient Languages (DAAL) Workshop.” Workshop, University of Ghent, June 27, 2024. <https://www.ghentcdh.ugent.be/data-driven-approaches-ancient-languages-daal-workshop>.
- . “Holocaust Testimonies as Language Resources.” Workshop presented at the LREC-COLING2024 Pre-Conference, Turin, Italy, May 21, 2024. https://www.clarin.eu/HTRes2024?fbclid=IwAR3jfuPj7TYmsk7vPJ941q7IMqFS_je9TIn1pvNDUrpRZtgLB_xRtxmW-54.
- Dejaeghere, Tess, Pranaydeep Singh, Els Lefever, and Julie Birkholz. “Exploring Aspect-Based Sentiment Analysis Methodologies for Literary-Historical Research Purposes.” In *Proceedings of the Third Workshop on Language Technologies for Historical and Ancient Languages (LT4HALA) @ LREC-COLING-2024*, edited by Rachele Sprugnoli and Marco Passarotti, 129–43. Torino, Italia: ELRA and ICCL, 2024. <https://aclanthology.org/2024.lt4hala-1.16/>.

Dejaeghere, Tess, Pranaydeep Singh, Els Lefever, and Julie M. Birkholz. “On the Creation of Multilingual Information Extraction Workflows for Literary-Historical Texts with Generative LLMs.” In *CLARIN Annual Conference Proceedings*, 18–21. Barcelona, Spain, 2024.
https://www.clarin.eu/sites/default/files/CLARIN2024_ConferenceProceedings_final.pdf

Eder, Maciej. “A Quick Tour Around the CLS Infra Project for Computational Literary Studies.” Presented at the Digital Humanities Lunch (DH Lunch), Online, February 11, 2021.
<https://dhlunch.ijp.pan.pl/en/11-02-2022/>.

———. “CLS INFRA: An Infrastructural Project.” Presented at the UNED-LINDH Conference, 2022.

———. “CLS INFRA Closing Event.” Workshop presented at the CCLS2025, Krakow, Jagiellonian University, Faculty of Philology, July 2, 2025. <https://jcls.io/site/ccls2025/>.

———. “Computational Literary Studies Infrastructure: Challenges in the Post-COVID Era.” Presented at the TwinTalks 4: Understanding and Facilitating Remote Collaboration in Digital Humanities, Graz, Austria, 2023.

———. “Digital Humanities Infrastructures: The Case of Computational Literary Studies.” Presented at the IAUPE 2023, Rome, 2023.

———. “From Research Infrastructures to Open Scholarship: The Case of Computational Literary Studies.” Presented at the DHSI2024, June 7, 2024.

Eder, Maciej, Bartłomiej Kunda, and Joanna Byszuk. “Computational Literary Studies Infrastructure and Open Science.” Presented at the The Polish Open Science Conference 2024, Krakow, April 11, 2024.

Edmond, Jennifer. “Literary Studies: Close, Distant, and Everywhere in Between.” Lecture presented at the ARIANE Meeting, Lyon, France, November 9, 2023.
<https://www.huma-num.fr/les-consortiums-hn/>.

Edmond, Jennifer, and Vera Yakupova. “What’s the Use? Exploring Academic Applications of (Computational) Literary Studies.” In *Digital Humanities 2023: Book of Abstracts*, 232–33. Graz, Austria, 2023. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8107704>.

- Fernández Guerrero, Eduardo. “TNA Seminar: Distant Reading of Early Modern Prophecies Across Europe.” Online meeting presented at the TNA Mini-Conference, LINHD-UNED, UNED, Madrid, Spain, April 24, 2024. <https://youtu.be/H43AyB5lvnM>.
- García Sánchez-Migallón, Patricia. “TNA Seminar: Eighteenth-Century Spanish Women Writers of Irish Descent and Social Network Analysis.” TNA Fellow Lecture, University of Galway, Ireland, May 28, 2024. <https://youtu.be/zmsa1QOzzY4?feature=shared>.
- Ghajari, Adrian, Víctor Fresno, and Enrique Amigó. “Plataforma de Exploración de La Composición Semántica a Partir de Modelos de Lenguaje Pre-Entrenados y Embeddings Estáticos,” 52–56. La Coruña, Spain, 2022. <http://ceur-ws.org/Vol-3224/paper13.pdf>.
- Giovannini, Luca, Daniil Skorinkin, Peer Trilcke, Ingo Börner, Frank Fischer, Julia Dudar, Carsten Milling, and Petr Pořízka. “Distributed Corpus Building in Literary Studies: The DraCor Example.” Zenodo, 2023. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.8228523>.
- Hoover, Sarah. “Resisting Erasure: Theatre, Performance, and Data Infrastructure Shaping Knowledge Landscapes.” In *New Horizons: Race and Performance*. Villanova, PA, USA, 2024.
- . “Synergies in DH Infrastructures: CLS INFRA.” In *IFTR2025*. Cologne, 2025. <https://tws.phil-fak.uni-koeln.de/iftr-2025>.
- . “Toolkits, Best Practices and Infrastructures: CLS Resources.” Columbia University, New York / Online, 2024. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.13907314>.
- Hoover, Sarah, and Anna Dijkstra. “Literary Methods for All: CLS INFRA – Unlocking a World of Words!” Poster presented at the DH2024: Reinvention and Responsibility, Arlington, VA, August 10, 2024. <https://dh2024.adho.org>.
- Janssen, Maarten. “TEITOK API - Programmable DH Corpora.” In *Digital Humanities 2023: Book of Abstracts*, 2023.
- Justin, Jyothi. “Digital Cartography and Feminist Geocriticism: A Case Study of Marichjhapi Massacre.” Online meeting presented at the TNA Mini-Conference, LINHD-UNED, UNED, Madrid, Spain, April 24, 2024. <https://youtu.be/spAMLncao94>.

- Kamovnikova, Natalia. “TNA Seminar: Studies in the Contemporary Clandestine Poetry of Resistance: Perspectives and Challenges.” Lecture presented at the Research Lunch series, ACDH-CH, Vienna, May 16, 2024.
- Marcenaro, Simone. “Digital Humanities and Medieval Romance Philology: Two Case Studies.” University of Galway, Ireland, July 3, 2024. https://youtu.be/4js7uo2c_T8.
- Milosev, Marko. “TNA Seminar: Words to Actions: How and If Ideology Translates to Violence in the Case of Interwar Fascists.” Online meeting presented at the TNA Mini-Conference, LINHD-UNED:, UNED, Madrid, Spain, April 24, 2024. <https://youtu.be/fTfwraYSToM>.
- “Module: Digging for Gold - Knowledge Extraction from Text.” Event / Training Module presented at the DARIAH-CAMPUS module, June 2, 2024. <https://hdl.handle.net/21.11159/019595c3-4def-768c-9c30-ba2aaebe69c1>.
- Mrugalski, Michał, Vera Maria Charvat, Ingo Börner, Matej Durco, Sabine Laszkovits, and Stefan Resch. “Finding Haiku – Enhancing Findability and Accessibility of Poetry Resources in Multi-Genre Collections across Different Languages.” In *Digital Humanities 2023: Book of Abstracts*, 125–27. Graz, Austria: Zenodo, 2023. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.8107746>.
- Neugarten, Julia. “TNA Seminar: Catching Feelings: Aspect-Based Sentiment Analysis for Fanfiction about Greek Myth.” Aspect-Based Sentiment Analysis for Fanfiction, University of Ghent, June 17, 2024. <https://event.ugent.be/registration/event/f199b87a-00d8-4454-8426-f4d6385914ad>.
- Neugarten, Julia, Tess Dejaeghere, Pranaydeep Singh, and Julie M. Birkholz. “Catching Feelings: Aspect-Based Sentiment Analysis for Fanfiction Comments about Greek Myth,” 217–31, 2024.
- Odebrecht, Carolin. “Computational Literary Studies Infrastructure.” Lecture presented at the SDC4Lit Lecture Series: Digital Archives, Research and Research Data Management, Online, July 13, 2021. <https://www.sdc4lit.eu/veranstaltungen/carolin-odebrecht/>.
- “Onboard onto DraCor. Prototyping Workflows to Homogenize Drama Corpora for an Open Infrastructure,” 2023.
- Pozo, Álvaro Pérez, Javier De La Rosa, Aitor Díaz, Salvador Ros, and Elena González-Blanco. “Streamlining Poetry Research with Averell.” In *DARIAH Annual Event 2024*

- Proceedings*. NOVA, Lisbon, Portugal, 2023.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.8167448>.
- Rebora, Simone, Joanna Byszuk, Maciej Eder, Berenike Herrmann, Suzanne Mpouli, and Pablo Ruiz Fabo. “DH2024 Workshop - Computational Literary Studies: How To Do Research Responsibly (Program).” Workshop presented at the DH2024, George Washington University, VA, USA, July 22, 2024. <https://doi.org/10.58079/122j8>.
- Resch, Stefan, and Matej Ďurčo. “VELD (Versioned Executable Logic and Data): Making Digital Workflows Reproducible in a Reliable Way.” Demonstration presented at the DARIAH AE 2024 | Workflows: Digital Methods for Reproducible Research Practices in the Arts and Humanities, Lisbon, Portugal, June 19, 2024.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13655424>.
- Rosa, Javier de la, Álvaro Pérez Pozo, Salvador Ros, and Elena González-Blanco. “ALBERTI, a Multilingual Domain Specific Language Model for Poetry Analysis.” In *DARIAH Annual Event 2024 Proceedings*. NOVA, Lisbon, Portugal, 2023.
<https://doi.org/10.48550/ARXIV.2307.01387>.
- Schöch, Christof. “Genre Analysis in Computational Literary Studies: The First Ten Years.” Paper presented at the Max Kade Conference 2024, University of Illinois at Chicago, November 15, 2024.
- Schöch, Christof, Julia Dudar, Evgeniia Fileva, and Artjoms Šeļa. “Multilingual Stylometry: The Influence of Language on the Performance of Authorship Attribution Using Corpora from the European Literary Text Collection (ELTeC).” In *Proceedings of the Computational Humanities Research Conference 2024*, 386–408. Aarhus, 2024.
<https://ceur-ws.org/Vol-3834/>.
- Sharma, Srishti. “TNA Seminar: Can a Book Make You Happy?” Seminar, Ghent, BE, July 4, 2022. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Z8TmBd96O8w>.
- Sluyter-Gäthje, Henny, and Peer Trilcke. “Poesie Als Fehler. Ein 'Tool Misuse'-Experiment Zur Prozessierung von Lyrik.” In *DHd 2022: Kulturen Des Digitalen Gedächtnisses*, 190–93. Zenodo, 2022. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.6328200>.
- Smedt, Koenraad De, Iulianna van der Lek, Henk van den Heuvel, Antonio Balvet, Maarten Janssen, Silvie Cinková, Amelia Sanz, Stavros Assimakopoulos, and Louis ten Bosch. “CLARIN in Training and Education.” In *Selected Papers from the CLARIN Annual*

Conference 2022, edited by Tomaž Erjavec and Maria Eskevich, 34–50. Linköping, Sweden: Linköping Electronic Conference Proceedings / CLARIN ERIC, 2023.

Soffiantini, Laura. “TNA Seminar: Studying Formulaic Expressions in Latin Funerary Epigraphy.” Seminar, Ghent, BE, October 25, 2022.

<https://www.ghentcdh.ugent.be/library-lunch-talk-laura-soffiantini-studying-formulaic-expressions-latin-funerary-epigraphy>.

Steimer, Haimo. “TNA Seminar: The Clash of the Modernists.” April 5, 2024.

<https://youtu.be/INGzYsfZo1A>.

Teichmann, Lisa. “TNA Seminar: Translational Trajectories of German Fiction in the German and Austrian National Libraries.” Lecture presented at the Research Lunch series, ACDH-CH, Vienna, May 28, 2024.

“TNA Seminar: Digital Humanities Outputs in the Light of Research Assessment Reform.” Moore Institute, University of Galway, December 14, 2023.

<https://youtu.be/zX66yjlw9Mc>.

Tonra, Justin. “Literary Methods for All: CLS INFRA.” Cork, Ireland, 2024.

<https://digitalhumanities-uk-ie.org/2024-annual-event/2024-programme/>.

Tóth-Czifra, Erzsébet. “CLS INFRA: Literature by Numbers.” Brussels, Belgium, 2023.

Trilcke, Peer, and Frank Fischer. “CLS INFRA.” Presentation presented at the Virtuelles Treffen des SPP Computational Literary Studies, Online, September 22, 2021.

Trilcke, Peer, Evgeniya Ustinova, Ingo Börner, Frank Fischer, and Carsten Milling.

“Detecting Small Worlds in a Corpus of Thousands of Theatre Plays. A DraCor Study in Comparative Literary Network Analysis [Conference Version].” Cologne, 2022.

https://github.com/dracor-org/small-world-paper/raw/conference-version/Detecting_Small_World_Networks_in_a_Huge_Multilingual_Corpus_of_Theater_Plays.pdf.

Van Rossum, Lisanne, and Maciej Eder. “Six Overlooked Good Habits in International Project Management.” 2022.

Van Rossum, Lisanne, and Artjoms Šeja. “CLS INFRA: The New Wave: Charting Skills Gap in Training for Computational Literary Studies.” KNAW Humanities Cluster, Amsterdam, NL: Zenodo, 2022. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.6411397>.

8.3. Appendix 4: Results of Further Training Survey

This survey was not anonymous, therefore the open answers cannot be made public. However, these charts show the usefulness of the survey in evaluating past training and planning for additional training during the extension period, Mar-Aug 2025.

Question 1 has 46 answers (Checkboxes)

"Training needs: If CLS Infra were to offer some more training opportunities on some of the topics below, which would be of most use to you? (check all that apply)"

Figure 13: Further Training Survey Question 1

Question 4 has 44 answers (Range)

Average rating: 5.8

"Do you think that participating in a CLS INFRA Training School and/or in the TNA programme had a positive impact on your professional career?"

Figure 14: Further Training Survey Question 4

Question 5 has 44 answers (Checkboxes)

"If you think that participating in a CLS INFRA Training School and/or in the TNA programme had a positive impact on your professional career, could you please let us know where you benefited? "

Figure 15: Further Training Survey Question 5

8.4. Appendix 4: Internal Communications Survey Results

Figure 16: Internal Communications Survey- About

Figure 17: : Internal Communications Survey: About respondents

Figure 18: Internal Communications Survey: Which tools?

Figure 19: Internal Communications Survey: Effectiveness

Figure 20: Internal Communications Survey: Other tools?

Figure 21: Internal Communications Survey: WP Comms 1

Work Package Team Communications 2: Quality

How clear is the communication you receive from WP team members?	4.1/5
How timely is the communication within your WP team?	4.0/5
Do you feel comfortable reaching out to WP team members with questions or concerns?	4.6/5

CLSIINFRA Internal Communications Survey

Figure 22: Internal Communications Survey: WP Comms 2

Project Comms 1:
How often do you communicate with CLSIINFRA project team members outside your primary work package?

CLSIINFRA Internal Communications Survey

Figure 23: Internal Communications Survey: Project Comms 1

Project Communications 2: Quality

How clear is the communication you receive from CLSIINFRA project team members outside your primary work package?	3.8/5
How timely is the communication with CLSIINFRA project team members outside your primary work package?	3.7/5
Do you feel comfortable reaching out to CLSIINFRA project team members outside your primary work package with questions or concerns?	4.3/5

CLSIINFRA Internal Communications Survey

Figure 24: Internal Communications Survey: Project Comms 2

Figure 25: Internal Communications Survey: Challenges

Figure 26: Internal Communications Survey: Improvements

Figure 27: Internal Communications Survey: Comments

8.5. Appendix 5: Infographics

Four infographics were developed. In slightly different formats they exist as animated video explainers, [animated web pages](#), and a4 posters suitable for dissemination to offices or in meetings.

Video: Computational Literary Studies for Galleries, Libraries, Archives and Museums (GLAM). Beyond Academia Playlist, 2025. <https://youtu.be/xYQ1dkJMYfM>.

Video: Computational Literary Studies for Journalists. Beyond Academia Playlist, 2025. <https://youtu.be/NfhCD3qmPbU>.

Video: Computational Literary Studies for Medical Humanities. Beyond Academia Playlist, 2025. <https://youtu.be/EXAdSsrMujk>.

Video: Computational Literary Studies for Policy Makers. Beyond Academia Playlist, 2025. <https://youtu.be/mfp1nFmCTI8>.

Hoover, Sarah. *Posters: Beyond Academia: Uses of CLS Tools and Methods for Journalists, Policy Makers, GLAM and Medical Humanities.* January 25, 2025. a4 x4. <https://zenodo.org/records/15212772>.

Click on an image for suggestions tailored to your field

Journalism	Policy Making	GLAM	Medical Humanities

Download an A4 poster for your office

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Figure 28: Beyond Academics webpage at CLSIINFRA.io, leading to specified infographic pages

</> CLSINFRA COMPUTATIONAL LITERARY STUDIES INFRASTRUCTURE

The power of storytelling for GLAM

CLS Tools and methods

Making access Equitable and Engaged

Leveraging CLS tools in line with digitisation processes offers opportunities for improving information literacy, overcoming budget constraints, and serving diverse populations.

Example: EHRI

(European Holocaust Research Infrastructure)

<https://blog.ehri-project.eu/about>

Method: Named Entity Recognition
 Algorithmically search vast collections of testimonials to identify all people, places, and institutions. These can then be linked to your catalogue and studied for context and relation.

CLSinfra has identified ways to use literature in policy making based on interviews with policy makers.

Find the report*, interviews, video explainers and more resources:
clsinfra.io/resources/beyond-academia

*D3.5: *Understanding User Requirements beyond Academic Research*, 2024.

Computational Literary Studies Infrastructure (CLSinfra) has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101004984.

Figure 29: Beyond Academia-GLAM poster

</> CLSIINFRA COMPUTATIONAL LITERARY STUDIES INFRASTRUCTURE

The power of storytelling for policy makers

CLS Tools and methods

Policy is complicated.

How can you connect policy to public experience?

Literature can help.

Use familiar narratives to make claims about the present and imagine the future.

Example: connect to Island Culture with Sentiment Analysis

Sentiment analysis: algorithmic review of large sets of text, i.e. novels, to locate and categorise opinions.

“tangible landmarks of people and nature” (positive)

“places of refuge” (positive)

“lost paradise” (negative)

“cultural crossroads” (neutral)

CLSI INFRA has identified ways to use literature in policy making based on interviews with policy makers.

Find the report*, interviews, video explainers and more resources: clsinfra.io/resources/beyond-academia

**D3.5: Understanding User Requirements beyond Academic Research, 2024.*

Computational Literary Studies Infrastructure (CLSI INFRA) has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101004984.

Figure 30: Beyond Academia-Policy Makers poster

</> CLSINFRA COMPUTATIONAL LITERARY STUDIES INFRASTRUCTURE

The power of storytelling for Medical Humanities

CLS Tools and methods

Integrated and ethical medicine is complex.

How do therapists and medical practitioners characterise the experience of illness, explore the ethical dimensions of medical processes, and help patients understand, connect and cope?

Example: Mind Style and cognition

Mind Style: algorithmically analyse linguistic patterns to represent a 'mental self' or 'world view'. Find resonances in attitudes and cognitive processing in fiction or autobiography.

Pillière, L. (2013). 'Mind Style: Deviance from the Norm?', *Studies in English Stylistics*.

CLSinfra has identified ways to use literature in policy making based on interviews with policy makers.

Find the report*, interviews, video explainers and more resources:
clsinfra.io/resources/beyond-academia

*D3.5: *Understanding User Requirements beyond Academic Research*, 2024.

Computational Literary Studies Infrastructure (CLSinfra) has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101004984.

Figure 31: Beyond Academia-Medical Humanities poster

</> CLSINFRA COMPUTATIONAL LITERARY STUDIES INFRASTRUCTURE

The power of storytelling for Journalists

CLS Tools and methods

Attention is valuable.

Leveraging fiction and the tools of CLS can provide creative inspiration, better narrative building, and connection to your audience.

Example: Emotions of London

Algorithmically analyse large collections of text to create visuals that show patterns such as the incidence of place names over time. Show the connection between literary narratives and contemporary issues.

See The Emotions of London project, Stanford Literary Lab (litlab.stanford.edu)

CLS INFRA has identified ways to use literature in policy making based on interviews with policy makers.

Find the report*, interviews, video explainers and more resources: clsinfra.io/resources/beyond-academia

**D3.5: Understanding User Requirements beyond Academic Research, 2024.*

Computational Literary Studies Infrastructure (CLS INFRA) has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101004984.

Figure 32: Beyond Academia-Journalists poster

8.6. Appendix 6: Newsletter Sample

This is the Fall 2024 newsletter. [Follow this link to read this edition.](#)

[View this email in your browser](#)

Dear Colleagues,

We hope you are well and enjoying the change of seasons.

Below you will find news and updates from the CLS INFRA community, including information on upcoming events, current activities, and project progress.

If you would like to subscribe to our newsletter, you can do so [here](#).

CLS INFRA Communications Team

WHAT IS CLS INFRA?

Computational Literary Studies Infrastructure (CLS INFRA) is a four-year partnership to build a shared resource of high-quality data, tools and knowledge to aid new approaches to studying literature in the digital age. The digital age offers challenges and opportunities for completing research on Europe's multilingual and interconnected literary heritage. At present, the landscape of literary data, methods, and tools is diverse and fragmented. Even though many resources are currently available in digital libraries, a lack of standardisation hinders their access and reuse. The European Commission-funded CLS INFRA project will help to build the shared and sustainable infrastructure needed to undertake literary studies in the digital age. The project will align these diverse resources with each other, with the tools needed to interrogate them, and with a widened base of users. The resulting improvements will benefit researchers by bridging gaps between greater and lesser-resourced communities in computational literary studies and beyond, ultimately offering opportunities to create new research and insight into our shared and varied European cultural heritage.

TNA FELLOWSHIPS

The CLS INFRA TransNational Access fellowship programme has entered its final round!

For more details, go to : <https://clsinfra.tna.sciencescall.org/>

The Programme provides access to a wide range of data, tools and knowledge. Scholars from literary studies or with an interest in **Computational Literary Studies** methods are invited to apply for a fellowship grant in one of our infrastructure providers. Successful applicants will not only obtain **free-of-charge physical access to the infrastructure**, but in the context of the overall project they will become part of the larger CLS community. By responding to one of our calls, applicants may have the opportunity to:

- Interact with experts;
- Receive advice on ongoing projects;
- Learn how to use the ecosystem of data, tools and standards;
- Assemble new literary corpora;
- Profit from hands-on training and support.

We also encourage applications from non-academic experts such as librarians, archivists, museum curators, journalists, policy experts, writers and other literary researchers.

For the 6th and final round, we will accept applications on a rolling basis with the following evaluation dates:

- **September 9, 2024** (notification mid-end September)
- **October 21, 2024** (notification early November)
- **November 25, 2024** (notification early-mid December).

Please note that the places still available are scarce and the call might close earlier than foreseen. Furthermore, we cannot accept applications **for fellowships finished later than February 28, 2025**. Please take this into consideration prior to your submission.

The institutions participating for the first evaluation deadline are the following:

- University of Galway
- Trier University
- Charles University

N.B. Only applications from scholars based in an EU member state or in a Horizon 2020 associated country are eligible for this final call as the limit of fellowships that can be offered to scholars based in non-EU or associated countries has been reached.

In the videos below, our TNA fellows discuss their experience or give presentations on their work. Find out more in the [TNA Archive](#) online.

<div style="background-color: #1a3d4d; color: white; padding: 5px;"> <p>EWA DATA-BUKOWSKA JACQUELONAN UNIVERSITY</p> <p>DISCUSSES A TNA FELLOWSHIP AT CUNI, PRAGUE</p> </div>	<div style="background-color: #1a3d4d; color: white; padding: 5px;"> <p>JANA MENDE HALLER LITERAR UNIVERSITÄT HALLE-WITTENBERG</p> <p>DISCUSSES A TNA FELLOWSHIP AT ACDH-CH, VIENNA</p> </div>
<div style="background-color: #1a3d4d; color: white; padding: 5px;"> <p>HAIMO STIEMER TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY OF DARMSTADT</p> <p>DISCUSSES A TNA FELLOWSHIP AT THE MOORE INSTITUTE, GALWAY</p> </div>	<div style="background-color: #1a3d4d; color: white; padding: 5px;"> <p>AGNIESZKA SZULIŃSKA INSTITUTE OF LIBRARY RESEARCH OF THE POLISH ACADEMY OF SCIENCE</p> <p>DISCUSSES A TNA FELLOWSHIP AT DH POTSDAM</p> </div>
<div style="background-color: #1a3d4d; color: white; padding: 5px;"> <p>BOTOND SZEMES HUMANITIES RESEARCH CENTER FOR THE HUMANITIES, INSTITUTE FOR LIBRARY STUDIES</p> <p>DISCUSSES A TNA FELLOWSHIP AT DH POTSDAM</p> </div>	<div style="background-color: #1a3d4d; color: white; padding: 5px;"> <p>RADIM HLADIK DEPARTMENT OF SCIENCE, INSTITUTE OF PHILOSOPHY</p> <p>DISCUSSES A TNA FELLOWSHIP AT CDH, TRIER UNIVERSITY</p> </div>
<div style="background-color: #1a3d4d; color: white; padding: 5px;"> <p>JULIA NEUGARTEN RABOLD UNIVERSITY KOBLENZ</p> <p>DISCUSSES A TNA FELLOWSHIP AT CHENT UNIVERSITY CDH</p> </div>	<div style="background-color: #1a3d4d; color: white; padding: 5px;"> <p>NATALIE KAMOVNIKOVA INDEPENDENT RESEARCHER</p> <p>DISCUSSES A TNA FELLOWSHIP AT ACDH-CH</p> </div>
<div style="background-color: #1a3d4d; color: white; padding: 5px;"> <p>LUCAS VAN DER DEIJL UNIVERSITY OF GIESSEN</p> <p>DISCUSSES A TNA FELLOWSHIP AT THE NETWORK FOR DIGITAL HUMANITIES AT THE UNIVERSITY OF POTSDAM</p> </div>	<div style="background-color: #1a3d4d; color: white; padding: 5px;"> <p>SIMONE MARCENARO UNIVERSITY OF SCIENCES, ECONOMICS, SOCIAL & DESIGN INNOVATION</p> <p>DISCUSSES A TNA FELLOWSHIP AT THE UNIVERSITY OF GALWAY</p> </div>
<div style="background-color: #1a3d4d; color: white; padding: 5px;"> <p>VLADIMIR POLOMAC UNIVERSITY OF ASSOCIATING FACULTY OF HUMANITIES AND ARTS</p> <p>DISCUSSES A TNA FELLOWSHIP AT CHARLES UNIVERSITY (CUNI), PRAGUE</p> </div>	<div style="background-color: #1a3d4d; color: white; padding: 5px;"> <p>BYUNCJUN KIM CENTER FOR DIGITAL HUMANITIES, COMPUTATIONAL SOCIAL SCIENCES, KAIST</p> <p>DISCUSSES A TNA FELLOWSHIP AT TRIER CENTER FOR DIGITAL HUMANITIES</p> </div>

Figure 33: CLS INFRA newsletter Fall 2024

D2.2 Final Report on Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation

RECENT DELIVERABLES

RECENT & UPCOMING EVENTS

TNA Mini-Conference, UNED

Three CLS INFRA TNA Fellows at LINHD-UNED in Madrid took part in an online mini-conference on 24 April, 2024. Each presented on their research and discussed their plans with each other.

- [Jyothis Justin, Digital Humanities and Publishing Studies Research Group, JIIT Indore. Project title: SEEING THE UNSEEN: LOCATING THE WOMEN OF INDEPENDENT INDIA'S UNHEARD DALIT MASSACRES](#)
- [Eduardo Fernández Guerrero, European University Institute: DISTANT READING OF EARLY MODERN PROPHECIES ACROSS EUROPE: CORPUS FORMATION AND TESTING](#)
- [Marko Milosev, Central European University, Vienna, Austria: WORDS TO ACTION: HOW AND IF IDEOLOGY TRANSLATES TO VIOLENCE IN THE CASE OF INTERWAR FASCISTS ORGANISATION](#)

TNA Seminar: The Clash of the Modernists

Haimo Stiemer was a CLS INFRA TNA Fellow at the Moore Institute, University of Galway, and works as a research associate at the Technical University of Darmstadt. Beside Computational Literary Studies, his areas of research include the literature of German-language modernism, Literary Sociology and Theory.

He presented this seminar at the University of Galway on 24 March 2024.

TNA Seminar: Eighteenth-Century Spanish Women Writers of Irish Descent and Social Network Analysis by Patricia García Sánchez-Migallón, CLS INFRA TNA Fellow

Several women writers of recognized prestige in Spain, born during the 18th century, had Irish ancestry. The project proposes to explore, on the basis of the personal connections that can be traced through

documents and literary-historical works, the different visualizations of their relationship graphs. The main hypothesis to be corroborated is whether the relationships maintained that connected them with their country of origin helped them in the publication of their works and, in each particular case, whether this help may have been motivated by the aim of disseminating enlightenment ideas. In principle, the project will focus on the figures of Margarita Hickey, Inés Joyes y Blake, María Gertrudis Hore, Frasquita Larrea and her daughter, Cecilia Böhl de Faber y Ruiz de Larrea. This seminar was recorded on 28 May 2024.

TNA Seminar: Catching Feelings: Aspect-Based Sentiment Analysis for Fanfiction about Greek Myth

Julia Neugarten was a CLS INFRA TNA Fellow at the University of Ghent CHD, and presented this seminar at the University on 17 May. Using aspect-based sentiment analysis (ABSA), Julia and her colleagues examine how several aspects of fanfiction about Greek myth are evaluated by commenters. In this presentation, Julia reports on the processes of data collection and annotation for the project, introduces the different aspects, describes the pipeline for aspect-based sentiment analysis and presents some preliminary results. Julia Neugarten is currently at General Cultural Sciences at Radboud University Nijmegen within the Anchoring Innovation project.

TNA Joint Seminar: Digital Humanities and Medieval Romance Philology: Two Case Studies

Floriana Ceresato (Università di Padova) and Simone Marcenaro (Università del Molise) were CLS-INFRA Fellows at the University of Galway. They are developing two projects in the field of Digital Humanities applied to Romance Philology: while [Floriana is working on a scholarly digital edition of the 13th century Franco-Italian version of the epic poem Anseïs de Carthage](#), Simone's project wants to explore the challenges and opportunities posed by AI translation in the literary realm, using Medieval Galician-Portuguese poetry as a focal point. In this joint seminar on 3 July 2024, they introduce and discuss these projects and accompanying methodologies.

Averell: A corpus management tool to transform poetic corpora into a JSON format compliant with the POSTDATA ontology (Poetrylab Suite, part 1)

Thank you to all who attended, taught and staffed the 2024 Training School! To hear about participants' experiences, check the videos below:

GET IN TOUCH

If you would like to know more about the CLS INFRA project, or would like to get in touch, please contact info@clsinfra.io.

Don't forget to follow and subscribe to our channels below.

This email was sent to cd@ml Address: info@cl / get this? unsubscribe from this list update subscription preferences
CLS INFRA - Moore Institute - NUJ Galway - Galway, Connacht Galway - Ireland

8.7. Appendix 7: Project Summary Posters

These A0 size posters were available for presentation at conferences and events. They summarise the project's objectives or achievements. CLS INFRA project members presented these at conferences listed in 8.2 Appendix 2: Scientific Conference Papers / Posters.

Figure 34: CLS INFRA Summary poster 2022

Figure 35: CLS INFRA Summary poster 2023

Figure 36: CLS INFRA Summary poster 2024

Figure 37: CLS INFRA Summary poster 2025